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**Experimental and numerical quantification of
influences of drugs on zebrafish larvae swimming
kinematic and energetics**

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Abstract

In this study, we have developed a novel methodology to investigate the influences of drugs on zebrafish larvae kinematics and energetics. Medical treatment of zebrafish larvae can directly influence its swimming behaviors. These behavior changes are related to functional changes of the central nervous system (CNS) and transformations of the zebrafish body, such as muscle mechanical power and force variation, which cannot be measured directly by pure experiment observation. The method includes the experimental study with MatLab post-processing and numerical simulation based on CFD software OpenFOAM to quantify influences of drug applications on zebrafish larvae kinematic and energetic performance, and especially internal muscle mechanics. Our numerical methodology has been compared with experimental results to validate its feasibility, and all the quantitative comparisons showed acceptable similarities.

Applications on our methodology include nociceptive and neuroactive drug influences on zebrafish locomotion and assistance made from part of our results on the evaluation of Gypenosides protection from high concentration acetic acid. Based on our results, our numerical simulation can successfully quantify the both kinematic and dynamic variation before and after drug treatment, such as velocity, head and tail angle, force and power generation, etc. The kinematic variations including velocity and tail bean angle are in consistent with experimentally observed results, and dynamic variations are also quantified to reflect the degree of muscle damage caused by drug treatment. These results provide novel insights into the reasons for pain-related behavioral changes in fish larvae, especially from an internal muscle perspective. Using this approach, we might focus on evaluating potential analgesic drugs for pain relief and neuroactive drug effects on fish behaviours, which might help to understand functions of nervous system.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Zebrafish (also called *Danio rerio*) is a tropical freshwater fish (displayed in **Fig. 1**) distributed across parts of India, Bangladesh, Nepal, and Pakistan (Rainboth, 1994). Over the past thirty years, zebrafish has become a pre-eminent vertebrate model to study genes as well as drug discovery and medical research. Zebrafish embryos have a nearly transparent body and develop externally (shown in **Fig. 2**), allowing scientists to observe the morphological changes such as cell motion, organ formation, heartbeat, and development during their first few days of life (Lieschke and Currie, 2007). Zebrafish can produce a large number of offspring, and the tiny body size allows massive specimens to be manipulated in a flexible space to generate a large number of mutants at the same time (Lawrence, 2007, Markovich et al., 2007). We can use the mutants to discover the specific stages of embryogenesis being disrupted by different types of mutations, which is essential for elucidating the conserved molecular mechanisms underlying early vertebrate development (Haffter et al., 1996, Mullins et al., 1994). Compared with human beings, zebrafish has a similar genetic structure and shares 70% of genes with human beings, which makes it achievable to study human diseases on zebrafish. In the following sections, a brief introduction of zebrafish applications and contributions in drug discovery and medical treatment will be stated to provide an essential background for readers on part of the research scopes of zebrafish.

Figure 1. A sketch of zebrafish development from the embryo stage (left-most image), larvae stage (medium image) to the adult stage (right-most model). (isoft iStock)

Figure 2. Development of zebrafish embryos in 1-day post-fertilization. The transparent body formation is advantageous to observe cell motion, organ formation, and heartbeat. (Lieschke and Currie, 2007)

1.1.1 Zebrafish contributions in toxicological study and new drug development

In recent years, zebrafish has become a valuable model for drug discovery. As shown in **Fig. 3**, publications on zebrafish related to toxicology have grown over 4-fold in the last ten years. At early stages, zebrafish larvae are cheap, and they can produce large numbers of offspring, from which scientists can test the efficacy and toxicity of new drugs before applying to expensive and complicated mammalian animals.

Toxicology, by definition, is tightly constrained to the need to prevent diseases. Specifically, whether a chemical is safe or a given disease is caused or influenced by a specific chemical exposure is at the core of the discipline. Therefore, evaluating the toxicity of a new drug is vital as the unaccepted toxicity will fail the check at clinical trials. Determination of toxicity includes various compounds such as heavy metals, pesticides, and compounds causing environmental contaminations. An important

parameter to be determined for toxicity testing is the LC₅₀ value (the concentration that is lethal to 50% of testing fish) (Gharedaashi, 2013). A comparison of LC₅₀ value between zebrafish and mammals based on 18 chemical compounds has been made, showing that zebrafish embryo is more sensitive to mammals for the toxic treatment (Belyaeva et al., 2009). Similar researches were also applied to evaluate the embryotoxicity and safety of drug application (Parng et al.).

Figure 3. Studies on zebrafish and toxicity studies with zebrafish. (Cassar et al., 2020)

1.1.1.1 Zebrafish as a model to study environmental toxicology

Early zebrafish models have been used to evaluate the environmental toxins more than pharmaceutical compounds (Caballero and Candiracci, 2018). Environmental toxins, including toxic heavy metals, endocrine disruptors, and organic pollutants, have been widely studied. Sandrine has tested the effect of MPTP, rotenone, and paraquat in both adult and larval zebrafish (Bretaud et al.). These neurotoxins can not only influence the aquatic environment but also induce Parkinson’s disease for human beings, which are meant to be studied. Decreased locomotor activity induced by MPTP has been observed on adult zebrafish, in contrast, larval zebrafish exhibited developmental, behavioral, and DA sensitivity to agents mentioned above, suggesting

that zebrafish could be a valuable model for testing of environmental toxins' effects. Other researchers have also studied similar researches in this field. Goolish tested the behavioral response of adult zebrafish to hypergravity conditions to prove that zebrafish can access the air-water interface for initial swimbladder inflation (Goolish et al.). Inspired by the fact that a mix of noxious agents can affect the aquatic embryo ignoring the protection of chorion, Merle studied the effects of single chemicals and chemical mixtures on zebrafish and medaka embryos' development (Dai et al., 2014). Part of the treated results on zebrafish were shown in **Tables 1 and 2**, and the author tested the effects of toluene and a mixture of TCDD and Benzene of dechorionated zebrafish. As displayed by two tables, dechorionated zebrafish embryos exposed to both single and mixed chemicals developed cardiovascular defects (Heart defects), and the mixture chemicals can cause more severe problems

Table 1. Survival of dechlorinated zebrafish after 30 min static exposure to toluene

	N	24 h	48 h	Heart defects *	72 h	96h (Swim up)
100 ppm toluene	10	2(20%)	2(20%)	2/2	2(20%)	0
10 ppm toluene	11	5(45%)	5(45%)	3/5	5(45%)	2(18%)
1 ppm toluene	36	25(69%)	21(58%)	1/21	20(56%)	17(47%)
0.1 ppm toluene	20	12(60%)	11(55%)	1/11	11(55%)	10(50%)
0.01 ppm toluene	20	15(75%)	15(75%)	1/15	14(70%)	14(70%)
0.001 ppm toluene	16	14(88%)	12(75%)	0	12(75%)	12(75%)
0.0001ppm toluene	16	13(81%)	13(81%)	0	13(81%)	13(81%)

Table 2. Survival of dechlorinated zebrafish after 30 min static exposure to a mixture of TCDD and Benzene

	N	24 h	48 h	Heart defects*	72 h	96 h (Swim up)
1 ppm TCDD/benz	16	6(38%)	4(25%)	2/4	4(25%)	2(13%)
0.1 ppm TCDD/benz	16	10(63%)	8(50%)	1/8	6(38%)	5(31%)
0.01 ppm TCDD/benz	16	16(100%)	16(100%)	0	11(69%)	8(50%)
0.001 ppm TCDD/benz	16	13(81%)	10(63%)	0	10(63%)	10(63%)
0.0001 ppm TCDD/benz	16	14(68%)	12(76%)	0	12(75%)	12(75%)

1.1.1.2 Zebrafish as a model in toxicology and drug discovery

By definition, drug discovery is the process of identifying potential new medicines, involving a wide range of scientific disciplines, including biology, chemistry, and pharmacology. Modern drug discovery involves the identification of high throughput screening (HTS), which requires significant investments by pharmaceutical companies, therefore, cost control for preclinical testing is necessary.

Following the 3Rs criteria, replacement, reduction, and refinement in animal research (Russell, MacArthur Clark), zebrafish is gaining its popularity as an alternative animal model. According to the European Commission Directive from 2010, experiments with the earliest life-stages of some animals are not regulated as animal models (Cassar et al., 2020). Therefore, zebrafish under five days post fertilization (dpf) can be considered as the earliest life-stage subject to regulation mentioned above.

Drug discovery used to be achieved occasionally by observing phenotype changes of whole animals exposed to small molecules. As zebrafish have high fecundity, a large

scale and systematic screening can be performed to study new drugs and toxicology. In drug discovery, the biological effects of toxins and chemicals have been studied extensively (Wiley et al., 2017). Peterson examined the impact of 1100 molecules with large scale screening on the central nervous system and heart of zebrafish embryos, and found that some molecules can disturb the development of embryos (Tamplin et al., 2012). Yu designed a screen to find a compound that could inhibit targeted bone morphogenetic protein (BMP) receptors (Yu et al., 2008). They have found an inhibitor called dorsomorphin which can perturb dorsoventral axis formation in zebrafish. As shown in **Fig. 4**, zebrafish applied with different concentration dorsomorphin can affect the formation of body trunk.

Figure 4. Dorsomorphin induces dorsalization in zebrafish embryos. (A) Structure of dorsomorphin. (B) WT zebrafish embryos at 36 (hours post-fertilization) hpf. Ventral tail fin is highlighted in brackets. (C) Zebrafish embryo treated with 10 μM dorsomorphin (DM) at 6-8 hpf and photographed at 36 hpf. (D) Zebrafish embryos treated with 10 μM dorsomorphin at 6 hpf, occasionally develop ectopic tails at 48 hpf. (Yu et al., 2008)

Besides, neurotoxicity are also widely concerned in drug discovery with zebrafish embryos and larvae. Neurotoxicity testing is the initial stage for studying mechanisms

of neurological disorders and diseases (Babin et al.). By definition, neurotoxicity represents a form of toxicity in which a specific toxin produces adverse effects on the function of a particular region of the central/peripheral nervous system (Cunha-Oliveira et al., 2008). As the central/peripheral nervous system controls the motor neurons in the spinal cord of fish embryos and thus the musculature, it is necessary to record the locomotion of fish samples to screen the neurotoxic compounds (d'Amora and Giordani, 2018). A wide range of drugs have been tested, such as diphenylhydantoin, pentylenetetrazol, and picrotoxin, to study the influences on locomotor behaviors (Li et al., 2018, Yang et al., 2017, Liu et al., 2016). Examples of part of those results are shown in **Fig. 5**. As shown in this figure, most researchers choose to use distance moved by the fish embryos during a period, which is the most straightforward parameter. The current results suggesting that the influences from neurotoxic drugs on locomotor activities are dose-dependent, compared with rodent animals; these results are proved to be similar (Cassar et al., 2020). Although there exist some untranslatable results, it is prudent to say that zebrafish can be an alternative model for neurotoxicity study.

1.1.2 Zebrafish contributions in human disease modeling

It has been reported that more than 80% of human genes associated disease have a zebrafish homolog (Howe et al., 2013), which means some common conditions such as muscle, cardiovascular and intestine diseases in human beings that cause changes to human body tissues could theoretically be modeled in zebrafish. However, some tissues and body parts with pathological changes in human beings do not exist in zebrafish, such as lungs should be examined with other animals.

Currently used genome editing approaches are called CRISPR/Cas9, or artificial site-specific nucleases such as zinc-finger nuclease, and transcription activator-like nucleases (Hwang et al., Doyon et al., Bedell et al., 2012). With these genome editing approaches, scientists can knock-in or knock-out the target genes in vivo to mimic

human phenotypes and observe the symptoms on mutant zebrafish. These models can also be used to test cures for the disease. Compared with other rodent lab animals, zebrafish's high fecundity can achieve a large number of samples being observed repeatedly.

Many severe diseases have already been studied with mutant zebrafish models, including muscle diseases such as Duchenne muscular dystrophy, and neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's disease (Babin et al., Widrick et al., Bassett and Currie, 2003, Guyon et al., 2007, Newman et al., 2014, Newman et al., 2011, Vaz et al., 2018, Makhija and Jagtap).

Muscular dystrophy

The critical feature of muscular dystrophy is a loss of muscle function, which will lead to necrotic and abnormally sized muscle fibers. This kind of degeneration of skeletal muscles is always fatal to human beings. Large screens of zebrafish genes have identified a large number of mutants that influence the muscle function, including mutations at different positions along body trunk. Here we take a specific locus, *sapje* (*sap*), as an example to display the affected muscle formation of the mutant zebrafish model. As shown in **Fig.6**, dystrophin is lost from the end of muscle fibers in *sap* mutant zebrafish model, the fiber of zebrafish with *sap* mutation detaches compared with wild type zebrafish,

Alzheimer's disease

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most common form of neurodegenerative disease. Unfortunately, no effective therapies have been developed. By definition, AD is characterized by progressive memory loss including impairment of speech and motor ability (Voisin and Vellas). Before zebrafish being applied as a model to study AD, rodent models have been extensively used to investigate the mechanisms of AD. Compared to rodent animals, zebrafish lack the complex cognitive behaviors. Still, they possess orthologous genes to those mutated in familial Alzheimer's disease

(FAD), which are difficult to observe in rodent animals (Newman et al., 2014). Scientists can investigate the functions of some relevant genes involved in FAD in mutant zebrafish such as the presenilin genes, blockage, and loss of presenilin gene expression that can lead to lack of production of motor neurons in the developing spinal cord of zebrafish larvae (Nornes et al., 2009). However, to better study the pathology of FAD with the zebrafish model, a deeper understanding of zebrafish's brain structure and function are required

A

B

C

Figure 5. Examples of locomotor behaviors of zebrafish treated with different neurotoxic drugs. (A) Distance moved by zebrafish larvae under continuous illumination followed by alternative light and dark conditions. Comparisons are made between the control group and 125 μM picrotoxin. (B) Average distance moved by zebrafish larvae per minute within 35 minutes under continuous illumination, followed by a 5 minutes' dark condition. Comparisons are made between the control group and 500 μM diphenylhydantoin. (C) Effects of pentylenetetrazol on averaged distances moved by the zebrafish larvae within 1-min time under both light and dark conditions. The horizontal axis represents the concentration of pentylenetetrazol. (Li et al., 2018, Yang et al., 2017, Liu et al., 2016)

Figure 6. Fiber detachment caused by mutation of zebrafish. The left picture is the wild type zebrafish model with dystrophin, and the right image represents the mutant zebrafish model which lacks dystrophin (Bassett and Currie, 2003)

1.2 Motivation & research aim

As mentioned above, in recent years, zebrafish have been extensively used in the research fields as an alternative of rodent animals for toxicology and drug discovery; at the same time, many zebrafish models have been built to test chemical influences on the physiology and behaviors of zebrafish. In this part, depending on the purposes of experiments, critical features of affected zebrafish under chemical treatment could be described with images of damaged/deformed body tissues or changing swimming behaviors characterized by distance traveled/body bending angle. These two aspects are connected as the damaged body tissue will probably affect the swimming behaviors as well. Inspired by the connections between body tissues and swimming behaviors, we intend to build a novel zebrafish model different from the traditional biological model, this model will help to understand the internal muscle mechanics

during swimming and quantify the effect of internal muscle before and after drug treatment.

The novel model aims at combining our advanced flow analysis technology and experimental tools to investigate the variation of zebrafish swimming behaviors subject to pharmaceutical influences. The experimental tools include a biological observation of the in vivo zebrafish locomotion and the subsequent data analysis. The developed flow analysis tool can simulate the swimming behaviors of zebrafish larvae to quantify several important swimming characteristics, including body forces and consumption that could not be acquired with biological experiments only. With assistance from flow analysis technology, we can quantify to what extent the tissue has been damaged from the toxins and compare the effect of different chemicals with specific values and percentages.

Besides, we intend to test the feasibility of the model with different types of drugs and chemicals, including neuroactive medicines and chemicals, which will stimulate the nociception of zebrafish. A drug-induced recovery from body pain is applied as well. Using this approach, our model could potentially contribute to studying the effects of new drugs on zebrafish larvae.

1.3 Thesis structure

The thesis has been divided into six chapters. A brief introduction about zebrafish and its biological implications are stated in Chapter 1. A review of the past research on different species related to nociceptive study and pain relief and comparisons to zebrafish have been discussed in Chapter 2. Methodology, including Experimental setup, animal treatment, drug application, and MatLab post-processing are shown in Chapter 3. CFD simulations on the zebrafish larvae model are also shown in the methodology chapter. Validations of the methodology regarding biological

observations, MatLab post-processing, and CFD software coupling have been displayed in Chapter 4 Applications on drug treatment of the zebrafish larvae, and pain relief with Gypenosides including biologically observed kinematic performance and CFD simulated kinematics and energetics results on zebrafish larvae locomotion are also displayed in Chapter 4. The conclusion of the whole work and discussions about future studies related to pain relief on zebrafish larvae will be given in Chapter 5.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Nociception study on mammalian

Due to the above advantages of zebrafish, in recent years, it has been widely used to study one of the most concerned topics, body pain. Pain has been defined as a “complex constellation of unpleasant sensory, emotional, and cognitive experiences provoked by real or perceived tissue damage and manifested by certain automatic, psychological, and behavioral reactions” (Terman and Bonica, 2001). For human beings, they experience these pains over extreme temperatures and pressures that could potentially injure tissues, toxic stimuli, and inflammatory mediators (Dubin and Patapoutian, 2010). Pains are perceived by a peripheral sensory neuron known as nociceptor, which distributes in skin, muscle, and joints and plays the role of sending potential threats to multiple brain regions via the dorsal horn of the spinal cord (Belyaeva et al., 2009). The concept of nociception is developed by Sherrington in 1910, inspired by the Latin *nocere*, which means ‘to harm’ (C.S.Sherrington, 1910). It is a sensory system of the peripheral and central nervous system to detect potentially harmful stimulus. Due to the origins of different stimuli, nociceptors can be mainly divided into three types, thermal, mechanical, and chemical nociceptors. A schematic diagram sketching the development of the perception of pain is shown as **Fig.7**. Once contacting potential harmful stimulus, the peripheral nociceptors will be activated, the noxious stimuli will be transduced into neuronal signals and transmitted the signals to CNS. Integration of this information in brain regions results in complex cortical structure responses, and finally, modulation occurs via reciprocal and descending tracts (Grubb and Pasvankas, 2019, Vardeh and Naranjo, 2017).

Figure 7. Development of the perception of pain (Müller-Schwefe et al., 2017)
 As mentioned above, pain can be induced by many factors such as temperature, pressure, and chemical substances, scientist followed these factors and a large number of animal models possessing nociception system had been developed to understand pain better before zebrafish model was applied.

Transmissions of nociception study started from mammalian such as rodents as they have many similarities to human beings such as anatomy, physiology, and genetics (Daniel Le Bars, 2001). Bennett and his colleagues found a peripheral mononeuropathy in adult rat that produces disorders of pain sensation like human beings (Bennett and Xie), postoperative behaviors such as hyperalgesia, allodynia, and spontaneous pain were found. Sluka examined the differences of pain processing from skin to muscle; the author has injected Capsaicin into rats' skin, muscle, and joint respectively and record the level of pain. They found that nociceptive processing from cutaneous tissue injury is different from that of grave tissue injury as the lasting time for dermal tissue and muscle are different for mechanical allodynia and heat hyperalgesia (K.A.Sluka, 2002). Similar research has been done by Hargreaves's team by providing a new method to measure thermal nociception in cutaneous hyperalgesia, which possesses higher bioassay sensitivity than the traditional way (Hargreaves et al., 1988).

Jean studied the effect of morphine sulfate solution (MSS) on signs of pain and wound healing in dogs with corneal ulcers. Twelve dogs were tested, and ten out of twelve dogs have artificially created corneal ulcer in the right eyes, these dogs are treated with 1% MSS and saline solution topically on the right eye to observe the effect on healing. The results indicated that 1% of MSS could provide analgesia and did not interfere with routine wound healing (Stiles et al., 2003).

Rajan tested whether the Carrageenan could produce long-lasting hyperalgesia except short-time acute inflammation. By injecting different concentrations of Carrageenan into rats' muscle and joints, a dose-dependent influence on chronic hyperalgesia of muscle or joint from Carrageenan has been proposed, supporting that injection on deeper tissues could result in long-lasting hyperalgesia compared to cutaneous insult (Radhakrishnan et al., 2003).

2.2 Nociception study on zebrafish

From an ethical point of view and compared with mammals' experiments mentioned above, vertebrates like fish, reptiles, and birds are lower in the evolution scale, thus less sentient (Schaeck et al., 2013). Considering the welfare of animals and the principles of the Three R's, vertebrates have becoming demanded for biomedical and behavioral research. In vertebrates, fish is used to study nociceptive pain. Different species have been considered to determine the existence of specific responses.

Rainbow trout is a commonly used species for biological research. Nathalie has tested the effect of acetic acid in conscious rainbow trout (Newby and Stevens, 2008). The author has injected saline, 2%, and 5% concentrations' acetic acid into the lip of rainbow trout and compared the behavior response with the control group. Part of the results are shown in **Fig. 8**. It depicts the recovery time comparison of respiratory frequency for all tested groups. The injection of acetic acid has significantly extended

the recovery time to pre-treatment levels of respiratory rate. The author's team has also compared their results with Sneddon's results (Sneddon, 2003, Sneddon et al., 2003), they did not observe similar rocking or rubbing behavior as reported in Sneddon's study, but different from Sneddon's treatments, the author did not anesthetize the fish in advance, which might be the reason for that disagreement. Also, without pre-treatment with anesthesia, the fish might be nervous as well, and thus under severe stress, this might also contribute to the different observation results.

Figure 8. Comparisons of Respiratory frequency for all tested groups (Newby and Stevens, 2008).

Studies related to nociception on fish have been divided into two controversial groups, debating whether fish have nociceptors and could perceive pains. Studies on three species of elasmobranch fish indicated that fish do not have nociceptors similar to mammals and human beings (Leonard, 1985, Snow et al., 1993, Rose, 2002) and stated the difference between responses to noxious stimulus from pain perception (Rose, 2002). They stand on the point that fishes lack the most necessary brain structure, a neocortex, for pain perception compared to human beings. The opposite party found that although some bird species do not have a neocortex, they were proved to be able to perceive pain as well (Stevens, 1992). Moreover, by using techniques in neuroanatomy and electrophysiology, scientists have confirmed the presence of nociceptors. As shown in **Fig. 9**, there exists A-delta and C fibers in

trigeminal nerves of rainbow trout, *Oncorhynchus mykiss*. In higher vertebrates, A-delta and C fibers in the trigeminal nerve convey nociceptive information to the brain (Sneddon, 2002). Sneddon also showed that rainbow trout could perceive pain by injecting noxious stimulus into trout lips. Several complex reactions were observed, such as rubbing of the lips against the sides of the container, which implies that trout could perceive pain instead of simple reflex responses (Sneddon, 2003). Until now, relationships between nociception and pain perception cannot be united but determined based on specific fish species.

2.2.1 Zebrafish behavior study with high-speed camera

Zebrafish, as a well-established laboratory model, could be excellent to study nociception. In mammals, there exist mainly two types of analgesics, one is opioids, and another one is Nonsteroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) (Malafoglia et al., 2013). The existence of these analgesics can validate that certain stimuli can induce pain to mammals. Zebrafish have opioid receptors in their body which has functional characteristics similar to mammals (de Velasco et al., 2009). Its effect has been tested by morphine, suggesting that opioids in zebrafish work identical to those in mammals (Lau et al., Norton and Bally-Cuif, Cachat et al.). Whereas considering the NSAIDs, two of the commonly used NSAIDs are aspirin and Ibuprofen. They will reduce inflammation but induce some side effects at the same time. Lopez has tested the effect of aspirin on behavioral changes after applying zebrafish to different concentrations' acetic acid, and the results indicate that receptors for NSAIDs exist in zebrafish (Lopez-Luna et al., 2017b). Moreover, toxicology studies addressed the effects of NSAIDs on freshwater vertebrates, including zebrafish, by showing that ibuprofen is rapidly absorbed by embryos and larvae (David and Pancharatna, 2009). Therefore, it is convictive to use zebrafish for nociception study.

A

B

Figure 9. (A) Section of the maxillary branch of the trigeminal nerve of the rainbow trout (x 400, scale bar = $4\mu\text{m}$) (B) Section of the maxillary branch of the trigeminal nerve showing the presence of A-delta and C fibers (x 1000, scale bar = $2\mu\text{m}$). (Sneddon, 2002)

As nociceptors can detect a direct or potential noxious stimulus and pass the signal to the spinal cord to control muscle contractions and trigger body deformation (Sneddon, 2019), it can be visualized and studied by observing behavioral changes of fish body. Thus zebrafish has been used as a pain model to study nociception effects. Swimming behaviors of zebrafish are traditionally captured with a high-speed camera shown in **Fig. 10** for the sake of tiny body size (Seth A. Budick and M. O'Malley, 2000). Seth has given a general introduction of locomotion repertoire of larval zebrafish, including prey capture, turning behaviors such as escape turns, routine turns, etc. The author explained how the neurons controlled the different swimming patterns and deduce that different neurons will be activated by signals from different swimming patterns.

Figure 10. High-speed camera captured zebrafish larvae motion within 80 msec. body curvatures of zebrafish larvae at each time step are shown. (Seth A. Budick and M.O'Malley, 2000)

Followed by various MatLab functions or other post-processing tools, different research purposes are satisfied. Muller has studied the three swimming patterns of zebrafish larvae at different ages, cyclic swimming, slow and fast starts (Muller, 2004). The author has found the midline of zebrafish at each instant of time to get the body wave envelop, as shown in **Fig. 11A**, based on these midlines, it is possible to derive some kinematic parameters such as tail beat amplitude and frequency, and swimming speed. From this point, the author has calculated the corresponding parameters for different ages' zebrafish larvae (shown in Fig. 9B-9D). The author has also compared his results with other species like eel (Müller et al., 2001b) and mackerel (Katz and Shadwick, 1998), and found that body wave amplitude increases along the larvae zebrafish body, which is in contrast to eel and mackerel, and even adult zebrafish. The author later extended his research on zebrafish locomotion by applying 2-D particle image velocimetry (PIV) technique to study the influence of the intermediate flow regime (Reynolds number). The author displayed flow generated during the cyclic swimming of a larva (as shown in **Fig. 12**); from the figure, it is evident that the flow pattern differs between the stiff anterior part and the undulating posterior part. It explains the form of vorticity from head towards tail and finally detached at the tail. The black arrow indicates the propulsive jets pointing in the opposite direction of forward motion. The author also compared wake differences between larva and adult zebrafish. As stated by the author, this might be caused by different Reynolds numbers as adult zebrafish swim under a higher Reynolds number. Besides, different morphologies of adult zebrafish might also influence the kinematic performance and forming of vorticity. This point has been further studied in corporation with Dr. Li with computational fluid dynamics, reporting the influences from fin fold (only in larva zebrafish) on zebrafish locomotion behaviors (Li et al., 2016).

Figure 11. Midline curves of zebrafish larvae and the calculated tail beat kinematics. (A) Sketch of the side view of a zebrafish larva and midlines in a fish-based frame of reference. Lateral position of tail tip (h , black), swimming speed (ΔU , thin red), lateral velocity of the tail tip (v , thick red), angle of incidence (α_i , opaque blue), and angle of attack (α_a , thick black) are depicted at (B) 2 dpf, (C) 5 dpf and (D) 7 dpf (Muller, 2004).

Figure 12. Flow generated during a tail beat of a cyclically swimming zebrafish larva (age three dpf). The left column indicates the vorticity field in the color map. The right column sketches the most relevant flow features, with vorticity generated at the head region (elongate ochre area) and travels along the body, detach at the tail. The black arrow indicates propulsive jets, which gradually reorients more caudally as it goes down the body (Müller et al., 2001b).

2.2.2 Nociception study on zebrafish

Depending on the development stages of zebrafish, chemicals will be injected into adult zebrafish's body trunk or lips (Gehrig et al., 2018). For zebrafish larvae, the fish samples will be submerged in the solution. Commonly used noxious stimulus include extreme temperature and pressure, and chemicals such as acetic acid, citric acid

(Hargreaves et al., 1988, Correia et al., 2011, Malafoglia et al., 2013, Malafoglia et al., 2014, Peter J. Steenbergen and Bardine, 2014, Lopez-Luna et al., 2017b, Taylor et al., 2017). Malafoglia and his team have developed a zebrafish model to study pain induced by extreme temperatures. The intense high or low heat will lead to burns of tissues and cause damage. The damage can be attributed to both inflammation and axonal degeneration (neuropathic-like pain). The author has tested two events linked to the onset of injury, one is the degeneration of axons innervating the affected tissues, and another one is the over-expression of specific genes in sensory tissues and found that both of them are conserved from zebrafish to mammals, suggesting that zebrafish larvae could be potentially used to study cellular and genetic networks related to neuropathic and inflammatory pain system in mammals. Curtright studied the temperature-related nociception with zebrafish in a different way (Curtright et al., 2015). The author focused on the temperature aversion of 5 dpf zebrafish larvae. As shown in **Fig. 13A**, zebrafish larvae tend to stay in 28.5°C, either it is colder or hotter. The application of AITC (an inflammatory compounds that can reduce the threshold of stimuli to invoke nociception responses) promotes thermal aversion and reverses cool aversion (shown in **Fig. 13B**). In this condition, when analgesics were used, such as buprenorphine, the temperature aversion can be reversed. As depicted in **Fig. 13C and D**, buprenorphine significantly reduced 24.5°C and 32.5°C aversion for both control and target group. Although there is no significant difference at different temperatures, it is prudent to judge that it is possible to model nociception in zebrafish larvae.

A

B

C

D

Figure 13. Temperature aversion assays with five dpf zebrafish larvae. (A) Control group zebrafish larvae with no other treatment, distribution of time larvae spent in the 28.5°C control zone when experimental temperature set as indicated. (B) Comparisons of time spent at 28.5°C between control group and AITC treated group (C) Comparisons of time spent at 28.5°C between control group and analgesic drug-treated group (D) Comparisons of time spent in 28.5°C between AITC treated group and analgesic drug-treated group (Curtright et al., 2015).

Correia proposed that zebrafish is an appropriate behavioral model of nociception and tested its sensitivity and robustness (Correia et al., 2011). He has applied two different doses of acetic acid to study the threshold level of nociception. He has also tested the effect of morphine analgesics. As shown in **Fig. 14A**, the fish activity shows a significant decrease after injection of 10% and 5% acetic acid compared to the control group. In contrast, after treated with morphine (shown in **Fig. 14B**), the fish activity increased, and the value is getting closer to control group, suggesting that as a commonly used analgesic drug, morphine works similar in zebrafish as human being and zebrafish with acetic acid is a reasonable model to test analgesics.

A

B

Figure 14. Time course changes in zebrafish activity after the injection of different doses of acetic acid (A) and morphine (B). In Figure A, the control saline solution group (black line) has a higher activity than 5% acid (green line) and 10% acid (red line). In Figure B, after injection of 3mg/kg morphine (light green line) and 6 mg/kg morphine (dark green line), the activity increases compared to 10% acid-treated group (red line) and the value is getting closer to the control saline group (black line) (Correia et al., 2011).

Observations on swimming behavior differences such as time spent active and average swimming speed can also reflect the influences of the noxious stimulus. As shown in **Fig. 15**, Taylor tested the acetic acid concentration influences on mean distance and swimming speed, compared with the untreated group, it is evident that acetic acid has a negative effect on the swimming speed and mean distance traveled (time spent active) (Taylor et al., 2017). Steenberger has tested the anti-nociceptive effect of buprenorphine on zebrafish larvae (Steenbergen and Bardine, 2013). The effect of acetic acid on zebrafish locomotion shows similar results compared to part of Taylor's results (shown as **Fig. 16A**), and it is also a supplement for the low concentration range of acetic acid. As depicted in **Fig 16B**, when the larvae are pre-treated with $0.1\mu\text{g/ml}$ buprenorphine, there is a reduction of increased locomotion activity due to the application of low concentration acetic acid. The author has also compared the levels of cyclooxygenase-2 (cox-2) in zebrafish larvae and found that activation of nociceptive pathways in a low-concentration acetic acid environment produced behavioral changes that were accompanied by changes in levels of cox-2. As the associated gene is involved in the nociceptive process (Bingham et al., 2006), it seems reasonable to say that the acid-induced behavioral changes can be attributed to nociception.

A

B

Figure 15. Taylor's results of acetic acid concentrations' influences on zebrafish's kinematic performance. (A) Mean distance in 20 minutes (B) Mean speed in 20 minutes. (Taylor et al., 2017)

Figure 16. Zebrafish sensitivity to chemical stimulus-acetic acid. (A) Locomotion activity of zebrafish under acetic acid concentrations ranging from 0-0.025%. (B) Influences of buprenorphine on acetic acid-treated zebrafish. Only zebrafish larvae pre-treated with 0.1 μ g/ml buprenorphine do not have a noticeable increase of locomotion activity (Steenbergen and Bardine, 2013).

Considering the verification of zebrafish larvae as a suitable model for nociception study, Lopez Luna has verified that unprotected five dpf zebrafish could replace the adult zebrafish (Lopez-Luna et al., 2017a). Based on the findings, Lopez has tested several new analgesic drugs. Starting from verifications on morphine, caffeine and another commonly used analgesia among human beings, expected protections of those drugs from noxious stimulus were found on zebrafish, such as heartbeat changes and vitality recovery (Rana et al., Sanchez-Simon et al., 2010, Abdelkader et al., Santos et al., 2017), proving that zebrafish could perceive pains and nociception of zebrafish works similar to that of human beings.

In conclusion, as the zebrafish (adult/larva) displays similar reactions to both rodents and human beings when experiencing pain, it can be a suitable model for nociception study and new analgesic drugs discovery

2.3 Pain relief research on zebrafish with Gypenoside

As the zebrafish pain model has already been constructed, pain alleviation and recovery are well-reasoned to be focused on studying the effect of analgesic drugs. Starting from ethanol and morphine, which are commonly used analgesia among human beings, expected recovery from a noxious stimulus such as temperature and chemicals were found on zebrafish after applied with these analgesic drugs, such as heartbeat changes and vitality recovery (Rana et al., Sanchez-Simon et al., 2010, Abdelkader et al., Santos et al., 2017, Sneddon, 2003). Behavioral improvements after analgesia treatments have also been studied with time spend active, body curvature alteration, and averaged velocity over a period (Lopez-Luna et al., 2017b, Lopez-Luna et al., 2017a).

Gypenoside, saponin extracted from *Gynostemma pentaphyllum*, has been widely used in the past centuries on human beings (Hsu et al., 2011). Nowadays, gypenosides has been approved by the Central Drug Administration of China to be used as a traditional Chinese OTC in clinics (Dong et al., 2018). It has been proved to have different effects, such as antioxidation, antilipidemic, neuroprotective, and inflammation reduction (Zhang et al., 2017). A previous study showed that the antioxidant effect had been validated with the protection of Gypenosides from oxidative stress on retinal pigment epithelium cells (Alhasani et al., 2018) and vascular endothelial cells (Li et al.). As shown in **Fig. 17A and B**, zebrafish treated with $5\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ showed more cell viability and decreased apoptosis caused by H_2O_2 , suggesting that Gypenoside could protect retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) cells from oxidative damage and offer therapeutic potential for the treatment of retinal degeneration. Besides, the effective extraction from Chinese plant has been proved to lower triglyceride, cholesterol and nitrite in acute hyperlipidaemia of rats. Also, Gyp has been tested to have anti-inflammatory effect on aortic lesions of rats and human osteoarthritis chondrocytes (Abdelkader et al., Quan and Qian).

Figure 17. The effect of H₂O₂ on cell viability and death rate. (A) Gyp treatment countered H₂O₂-induced toxic effects. (B) Apoptotic cell number was quantified in 300 cells and presented as a percentage (Alhasani et al., 2018).

However, protection of Gypenosides on zebrafish were rarely discussed, only includes oxidative stress related to retinal degeneration (Alhasani et al., 2018), and most of the biological study including the zebrafish pain model study mainly focused on the kinematic and hydrodynamic performance caused by the surrounding fluid but desalinated the effect of internal muscle mechanics. The locomotion of fish larvae is powered by axial muscle system driven by motoneurons in the spinal cord (Voesenek et al., 2016a). Swimming kinematics are influenced by internal body mechanics and fluid mechanics (Eric.D.Tytell et al., 2010, McMillen and Holmes, 2006), forces generated by muscle induce body deformation, and the deformation will change the fluid dynamics of the surrounding water, i.e., hydrodynamic force. In return, this hydrodynamic force changes the body deformation as well (Voesenek et al., 2018b). Under this circumstance, these coupled mechanical interaction determines the motion of the fish through the water. Therefore, internal body mechanics are significant in the study of body motion.

2.4 Fish swimming performance study with Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV)

The above mentioned biological study mainly focused on the kinematic performance caused by the surrounding fluid but desalinated the effect of internal muscle mechanics. Observations and quantifications of only distance traveled, and velocity are not useful in ascertaining the influence of drugs on fish swimming behavior. Fish swimming kinematics are controlled by consecutive contractions of muscles located along each side of the body (Eric.D.Tytell et al., 2010, McMillen and Holmes, 2006). The muscle contractions are directly driven by motoneurons in the spinal cord, which is part of the central nervous system (CNS) (Ekeberg et al., 1995). The abnormal body contractions triggered by nociceptors will change the swimming behavior of zebrafish powered by axial muscle system (Voesenek et al., 2016a). Forces generated by muscle induce body deformation, and the deformation will change the fluid dynamics of the surrounding water, i.e., hydrodynamic force. In return, this hydrodynamic force changes the body deformation as well (Voesenek et al., 2018b). Under this circumstance, these coupled mechanical interaction determines the motion of the fish through the water. As some of the noxious stimuli could cause damage to fish body and muscle, it is worthwhile to study internal muscle mechanics, and a useful tool to quantify the association between the effect of drugs on zebrafish swimming behavior and energetics is required.

Applications of particle image velocimetry (PIV) techniques enables visualization of the flow field around the fish, and calculation of resultant hydrodynamic force (Li et al., 2012). A sample apparatus and resultant images are shown in **Fig. 18**. However, it is limited to the 2-D flow field, which will automatically ignore the flow passing through the dorsal and ventral side of the fish, and the resultant hydrodynamic force will not be accurate enough to describe fish's swimming performance. Although 3-D PIV can compensate for the deficiency, its high cost makes it not universally applicable to a majority of researchers.

A

B

Figure 18. (A) PIV apparatus used to measure flow patterns and kinematic performance of fish (B) Resultant velocity and vorticity field of a cruising fish. The time interval between consecutive snapshots is $1/32$ s. (Li et al., 2012)

Many recent studies have presented flow field measurements using PIV techniques. Muller has applied a 2-D PIV technique to study the interactions between body movement of eel and the surrounding fluid (MÜLLer et al., 2001a). As shown in **Fig. 19**, the author plotted the wake generated behind the eel body, and deduce that the wake structure is determined by phase lag between the vorticity shed from the tail and vortices produced along the body. Besides, the author suggests that eels can achieve different propulsive mode by adjusting their body wave. Tytell and his team studied the hydrodynamics of American eels systematically with high-resolution PIV to quantify wake structure, swimming efficiency, and force and power output. They compared the results with other species (Tytell and Lauder, 2004). A sketch of force and power from the PIV technique and elongated body theory is shown in **Fig 20**, indicating that lateral force is pulsatile. Compared with the PIV method, elongated body theory has underestimated the values of force and total power, as depicted in **Fig. 20B**. Besides, the author stated the differences of wake structure between an eel and carangiform swimmers, such as lacking of significant downstream flow for eels.

Figure 19. Instances during the time course of wake generation behind a steadily swimming eel. The black arrow indicates the swimming velocity, and blue shades indicate clockwise vorticity, red shades indicate counterclockwise vorticity. Darker shades indicate a higher level of vorticity (MÜLLER et al., 2001a).

Figure 20. Representative traces for force, impulse, and power from large-amplitude elongated body theory (black curve) and particle image velocimetry (red and green curve). Each black line shows force and energy for a single tail beat (Tytell and Lauder, 2004).

2.5. Fish swimming performance study with CFD simulation

Another popular method used to study interactions between fish and surrounding fluid is computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation. Compared to PIV method, CFD simulation has less limitations on fish body characteristics such as length and weight, after setting up body kinematics according to real fish, simulations on hydrodynamic forces can be more systematic and accurate, and the cost is much lower than PIV experiments. In previous studies, the hydrodynamics of aquatic locomotion relied on

the assumption that the water is inviscid (J. Lighthill, 1971, Wu, 1971). Some other researchers consider that it is necessary to quantify viscous effects to calculate drag forces acting on the body more accurately, and this requires CFD techniques. Starting from a simple aquatic model, Liu and his team studied the fluid dynamics of a swimming tadpole. The author discussed the mechanisms of thrust generation and flow patterns of swimming of both 2-D and 3-D tadpole models (Liu et al., 1996, Liu et al., 1997). As shown in **Fig. 21A and B**, variation of thrust, power, and drag coefficients due to friction are plotted against time. Although the time ranges are different for 2-D and 3-D tadpole models, it is evident that the factors are significantly varied between 2-D and 3-D tadpoles. Moreover, there is a non-zero net thrust value for 3-D tadpole, and as the models are forced to swim in an incoming flow with constant speed, zero net thrust indicates trimmed swimming. Therefore, the 3-D model is more realistic to represent the real tadpole swimming.

Figure 21. Variation of coefficients of thrust, power and drag due to friction plotted against time for the virtual swimming 2-D (A) and 3-D (B) tadpole (Liu et al., 1996, Liu et al., 1997).

Carling has built a 2-D anguilliform fish model with shape in the form of a backward-traveling wave with increasing amplitude from head to tail, and the fish model is constrained by lateral displacement equation and the equation describing the shape of the fish body is expressed as Eqn 1. In the equation, s represents the distance along the body measured from the nose, l is the total length of the body, and b is an

amplitude parameter used to allow an amplitude other than zero at the nose of the creature, whose value is 0.25 in the paper. Flow around the self-propelled animal was presented, as shown in **Fig. 22A**, other factors such as mean swimming speed and net force in x and y direction have been calculated as well (shown in **Fig. 22B and C**)(Carling et al., 1998). Kern has built a three-dimensional self-propelled anguilliform fish model to study the fluid-body interactions shown in **Fig. 23A**, not only the quantitative information, but also the different swimming modes are linking the kinematic of the motion with the forces acting on the body. He has also compared with two-dimensional condition with the existing data from Carling to study the role of 2-D and 3-D in quantifying the fluid dynamics, and the results are shown in **Fig. 23B and 23C**. It can be seen that compared with the 3-D model, swimming velocity is significantly higher for the 2-D case, and the structure of the vorticity is different as well. Besides, an optimization of swimming efficiency and burst swimming speed is provided. (Kern and Koumoutsakos, 2006). Borazjani has expanded the study of 3-D fish model interactions with fluid to different types of fish locomotion, including carangiform and anguilliform as the Reynolds number and Strouhal number can be systematically varied. The author discussed the differences of fluid dynamics between anguilliform and carangiform swimmers and the effects of Reynolds number and Strouhal number on forces and swimming efficiency. As depicted in **Fig. 24**, the sketch of time history of the axial force for both anguilliform and carangiform virtual swimmers shows similarities and differences between the two swimmer types. For instance, for all St values, there exist two peaks of the axial force coefficient in each cycle. However, the amplitude of the fluctuations above the mean value of the axial force coefficient is different, for which carangiform shows higher fluctuation amplitudes. Also, differences exist between two modes of swimming, such as wake structure (single row of vortices for carangiform and double rows of vortices for anguilliform) and Froude efficiency, at the same time, some aspects of undulatory locomotion do not depend on the specific mode of swimming. For example, for a given Reynolds number, there is a unique Strouhal number at which body undulations

produce sufficient thrust to cancel the hydrodynamic drag (Borazjani and Sotiropoulos, 2008, Borazjani and Sotiropoulos, 2009).

$$y_s = \frac{(s/l+b)}{1+b} \sin[2\pi(s/l)-t] \quad (1)$$

Figure 22. Results for Carling's paper on (A) streamlines in the wake region of a forward traveling 2-D fish model (B) forward and lateral velocity of the centre of mass and (C) forward pressure and drag for on body. (Carling et al., 1998)

Figure 23. Results for Kern's paper on (A) 3-D anguilliform fish model (B) Velocity comparisons between the 3-D case and 2-D case, the black curves represent longitudinal velocity (solid line) and lateral velocity (dashed line) for the 3-D example, and the cyan curves represent velocity for the 2-D case. (C) Vorticity comparisons for 3-D (right) and 2-D (left) case. (Kern and Koumoutsakos, 2006)

Figure 24. Time history of the axial force coefficient normalized by the rigid body drag coefficient for different St at $Re4000$. (A) Anguilliform virtual swimmer (B) Carangiform virtual swimmer. Positive and negative values indicate thrust and drag force, respectively (Borazjani and Sotiropoulos, 2009).

So far, the mentioned researches mainly focused on cyclic swimming of adult fish, but ignores the unsteady swimming of larvae fish. Aiming at making up for this part of the study, Katumata has built a 3-D zebrafish larva model to study the kinematics and hydrodynamics of a self-propelled swimming larva fish (Katumata et al., 2009). The zebrafish larva model is built based on the real zebrafish larva outline and is shown in **Fig. 25A**. When a fish starts swimming from stand-still, an acceleration happens, and the fish will bend its body into a C shape, which is called C-starts. The phase comprises a preparatory and a propulsive stroke. As shown in **Fig. 25B**, when the fish starts to bend the body, a blue vortex is formed behind the tail tip at $t=1/4T$ and followed by a red vortex generated at the tail tip at $t=2/4T$. However, the first blue vortex is not strong enough and dies off quickly, which makes the first vortex ring not complete. The complete vortex ring starts from the propulsive stroke. A much clearer sketch of the process of C-start is displayed in **Fig. 25C**. Kinematic and hydrodynamic results are shown in **Fig. 26**, force, power, and velocity of the C-start phase are

depicted and compared with the following stage. It is evident that during C-start, the speed experiences a sudden increase, followed by a relatively steady time range, and ends with a decrease. Compared to the following phases, the highest velocity values exist during C-start.

A

B

C

Figure 25. (A) Sketch of zebrafish model extracted from the real fish larva outline. (B) Iso-vorticity surfaces in the burst phase. (C) Real-time image of the C-start process, the left figure represents a stand-still state, the central number represents preparatory stroke, and the right figure represents a propulsive stroke (Katumata et al., 2009, Li et al., 2011).

Figure 26. Time variation of instantaneous thrust, friction and pressure drag (A) power (B), and speed (C) (Katumata et al., 2009).

Li provided a more systematic computational study on the kinematics and hydrodynamics of a 3-D zebrafish larvae model (Li et al., 2012). They studied the kinematic and hydrodynamic performance of cyclic swimming and spontaneous C-start, and compared results with the 2-D particle image velocimetry to prove that CFD simulation can accurately predict fish locomotion. As shown in **Fig. 27**, the author examined the flow patterns generated during cyclic swimming between CFD simulation and PIV results. In this figure, the author displayed similarities and slight differences between CFD and PIV results and explained the possible reasons, supporting the view that CFD simulation can accurately predict the motion of zebrafish larvae. Similar to what have done by Katumata, the author has also evaluated the swimming speed of zebrafish larva but included comparisons with experimental results. As shown in Fig. 28, it is evident that the simulated forward speed matches well with the experimentally measured results, which consolidates the simulation results on the hydrodynamic part. Li has also studied the fin fold influences of zebrafish larvae on vorticity and propulsion based on his previously built zebrafish larvae model (Li et al., 2016). By excluding the fin-fold structure (shown in **Fig. 28**), the author found that the fin fold helps larva achieve higher swimming speeds, yet requires high power. Therefore, the author suggests that the

propulsion of zebrafish larva, partly relies on the fin fold structure, providing a persuasive explanation for the omnipresence of the fin fold in bony-fish larvae.

Figure 27. Comparison of flow patterns between CFD and Experimental PIV results. The computational results are shown with two planes, one is the medio-frontal plane (left column), and another one is 0.6L below medio-frontal plane (center column), which is close with the position of PIV plane (right column). Slight differences in flow patterns between CFD results and PIV results might be caused by weak turning maneuvers of the CFD fish model, which may lead to imperfect and unsymmetrical cyclic swimming. (Li et al., 2012)

Figure 28. Velocity comparison between Experiments and CFD simulation of self-propelled zebrafish larva.

In our study, inspired by previous work involving Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulation on fish swimming (Borazjani and Sotiropoulos, 2008, Borazjani and Sotiropoulos, 2009, Carling et al., 1998, J. Lighthill, 1971, Kern and Koumoutsakos, 2006, Li et al., 2012), a novel nociception-related zebrafish larvae model combining a biological methodology and a CFD simulation analysis tool to quantify drug influences on zebrafish locomotion has been developed and described in the thesis. Specifically, we used not only observation of live zebrafish swimming behavior with a high speed camera, but also a CFD simulation tool to quantify several important swimming characteristics, including body forces and consumption power, which are hard to acquire with experiments only. By applying appropriate solid-body simulation toolbox and coupling with CFD software, internal forces, torque, and energy could also be quantified. Therefore, it is worthwhile to use CFD software to assist in the analysis of drug influences on zebrafish locomotion.

3. Methodology

A brief introduction of methodology

We intend to simulate the real zebrafish motion with the help of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) software OpenFOAM (<https://www.openfoam.com/>) and solid multibody motion solver MBDyn (<https://www.mbdyn.org/>). The actual fish motion is captured with a high-speed camera and post-processed with in-house MatLab code. Details of the methodology are stated in the following sections.

3.1 Experimental Motion capture & Post-processing

Apparatus

Apparatus shown in **Fig.29** is used to record the fish motion for further analysis. Zebrafish larvae (in all of our experiments, we used five dpf (days post-fertilization) zebrafish larvae) were put inside the Petri dish, and the diameter of the Petri dish is 100mm. High-speed camera right above the petri dish will record the motion of the fish with 500 fps setup. Due to the limitations of our post-processing tools, each time only one zebrafish larva locomotion was recorded. Depending on different treatments, fish larvae might be pre-treated before five dpf. Still, all of the zebrafish larvae will be allowed for 10 minutes to acclimate to the environment before the camera starts recording. The recorded videos will be collected and post-processing with in-house MatLab code. The experiments were carried out in a room maintained at $27 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. Water temperature was set at 27°C for each group, and the water was kept in homothermal water tank.

Figure 29. Apparatus used to record zebrafish larvae motion. The recorded video will be stored in the computer and processed with MatLab code

Ethics statement

Animal work was carried out in compliance with the Animal Ethics and Welfare Committee, Department of Life Sciences, Glasgow Caledonian University, and UK Home Office under Project License PPL 60/4169.

The methodology of the experiment was divided into two parts, the first part is validation experiments including multiple types of medicine and drugs, and the second part is the protection of zebrafish larvae from acetic acid with Gypenosides (GYP) with qRT-PCR analysis.

3.1.1 Validation experiment

Experiment setup

The experiment setup and main methodology were developed based on our previous study for the determination of the toxicity of acrylamide on zebrafish locomotion via a colour preference experiment (Jia et al., 2017). In the present study, eighty five dpf (day's post-fertilization) wildtype zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) larvae siblings were used in

this part, and divided into four groups. Any larvae not used in the present study were kept for further experiment or humanely killed before reaching six dpf with MS-222. All fish were immersed in E3 medium (5mM NaCl, 0.17mM KCl, 0.33mM CaCl₂, 0.22mM MgSO₄, and 0.1% methylene blue) initially, with one hours' time to adapt to the environment. The larvae will then be gently placed individually into four Petri dishes, with twenty larvae in each Petri dish. The first one with E3 medium, and the second one with 0.01% acetic acid solution, the third one with 500 μ M diphenylhydantoin (DPH), and the fourth one with 100mg/L yohimbine solution (yohimbine hydrochloride), to avoid group interactions. Each larva had ten minutes to stay in the petri dish before observation commenced and will be gently moved to the prepared petri dish for recording. The petri dish was illuminated by a light-emitting diode (LED) panel, driven by an adjustable DC power supply (CSI5003XE, Circuit Specialists, and the USA) to provide a continuous and constant light. A high-speed video camera (Mikrotron EoSens CL MC1362) was used to record fish swimming behavior. The frame rate of the camera was set at 500 frames per second (fps) during the entire experiment process. As in the subsequent CFD numerical modelling, the selected fish with a tail beat frequency being less than 70Hz; thus, 7-8 frames within one beat cycle is sufficient to capture the fish tail motion and extract the motion equaitons. Once recording commenced, there was no stimulation to force the fish swimming forward. In this study, only the quasi-steady cruising swimming regime is investigated, excluding the burst-start process. The limitation is evident from previous research that cruising with cyclical motion is essential for fish larvae to cover the distance for migration and dispersal (Sancho et al., 1997). Besides, cruising swimming has been studied extensively, which makes it easier to compare with other researcher's results. In the post-processing part with MatLab, we will select frames containing cyclic swimming behaviours for further processing. Zebrafish fish larvae were then gently moved from the petri dish and humanely killed with MS-222 once the experiment is finished.

3.1.2 Application Experiment

3.1.2.1 Zebrafish locomotion recording

The experiment was divided into two parts, and the first part is the observation of zebrafish locomotion under different treatments to study Gypenosides (Sigma-Aldrich, UK) protections from high concentration acetic acid damage on zebrafish larvae. Eighty four dpf zebrafish larvae have been prepared and divided into four groups. Group 1 and group 2 were treated with $5 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ GYP solution, group 3 and group 4 were treated with E3 medium (5mM NaCl, 0.17mM KCl, 0.33mM CaCl₂, 0.22mM MgSO₄, and 0.1% methylene blue) only. The zebrafish larvae were stayed in homothermal incubator at $27\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and lasted for one day. At five dpf, larvae in group 1 and group 3 were treated with 0.1% acetic acid, and the other two groups remained unchanged as control groups. For all groups, fish larvae stayed under the camera and swam freely without any environmental or factitious influence. Swimming behaviours of all the fish samples were recorded for ten minutes and post-processed with in-house MatLab code to be prepared as input for the CFD simulation.

3.1.2.2 Quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction (qRT-PCR)

The second part of the experiment is the toxicity tests of acetic acid, and Gypenosides protection (Sigma-Aldrich, UK) performed in 48-well plates. All experiments were performed in triplicate wells, which contained ten embryos in 400 μl drug solutions. The sample was exposed to 0.1% Acetic acid, 0.1% Acetic acid+5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ GYP, 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ GYP as well as an untreated group.

Total RNA was isolated from untreated and treated zebrafish embryos with 120 hours post-fertilization (hpf) using Trizol Reagent (Sigma, UK) according to the manufacturer's guidance. The complementary deoxyribonucleic acid (cDNA) was synthesized using a High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Applied

Biosystems, UK). The quantification of genes expression was measured by qRT-PCR assay using a Platinum® SYBR® Green PCR kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, UK) under the PCR condition as described in the protocol. Relative expression of the target gene was determined by normalization to the expression of the housekeeping gene (β -actin) in the untreated and treated samples, using $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ formula. The primer sequences of the genes used are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Primers used for qRT-PCR

Genes	Forward primers 5'-3'	Reverse primers 5'-3'	TM°C	PCR product (bp)
β -ACTIN	ACTGTATTGTCTGGTGGT AC	ATCTCCTGCTTGCTAATC C	69.7	198
IL-1 β	TTCCCCAAGTGCTGCTTA TT	AAGTTAAAACCGCTGTG GTCA	54.6	149
IL-6	TCAACTTCTCCAGCGTG ATG	TCTTTCCCTCTTTTCCTC CTG	55.1	75
TNF- α	ACCAGGCCTTTTCTTCAG GT	GCATGGCTCATAAGCACT TGTT	56.5	147
SOD1	CGCATGTTCCCAGACATC TA	GAGCGGAAGATTGAGGA TTG	53.9	100
SOD2	CTAGCCCGCTGACATTAC ATC	TTGCCACATAGAAATGC AC	54.5	101
GPX1	AGGCACAACAGTCAGGG ATT	CAGGAACGCAAACAGAG GG	56.45	241

Statistical analysis

Graphpad Prism (version 7.0 from Graphpad Software Inc. San Diego, CA, USA) has been used for statistical analysis. All multiple comparisons were performed using the

one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni multiple comparison test. Statistical significance was considered when a level of p is less than 0.05.

3.1.3 Data processing algorithm

An in-house MatLab code was developed and used to post-process the recorded videos and extract zebrafish swimming kinematic characteristics, i.e. body curvature equations. A real zebrafish larvae picture taken from our high-speed camera is shown in **Fig. 30A**, and the full path of fish motion can be extracted as well (shown in **Fig. 30B**). Key steps of body curvature extraction are shown in **Fig.30C**. The entire video will be divided into frames, and each frame is expressed as the original image. The original image is converted to a binary image consisting of the sketch of zebrafish larvae with the help of '*im2bw*' function in MatLab image processing toolbox to get rid of unwanted parts in the picture such as edges of the petri dish and impurities. With some adjustments and '*bwboundaries*' function in MatLab, a binary image of zebrafish can be extracted, the entire position vector expressed as (x_i, y_i) can be obtained for points distributed on the fish outline. x_i and y_i are expressed as pixel values and will be converted to the SI unit of length for further calculations. All images were skeletonized into a single backbone curve using functions '*bwmorph*' and '*thin*' operations.

The coordinated pixels on the backbone curve were then divided into equal-distant curves, and each curve represent one body segment. These segments were simplified as connected straight lines to calculate relative orientation variation with time between two adjacent segments using MatLab curve fitting toolbox. Physical representation of the intersection angle is shown in **Fig. 30D** and the 3-D intersection angle is expressed by **Fig. 30E**, and calculated with Eqn 1, where i denotes points numbering from one. In **Fig. 30D**, each each straight black line represent one segment of the fish body, the prescribed relative orientation can mimic the body curvature, and

angular displacement represents the lateral displacement of the fish body. As elucidated by (Muller, 2004), the travelling wave of curvature travels along the fish body at a near-constant rate. Thus an averaged frequency was selected for the entire relative orientation functions along the body. The detailed extracted relative orientation values are shown with Table 4. Eqn 2 represents a sample prescribed deformation equation for relative angle between each two body segments, and a set of sample equations are written in Table 5. **Fig 30F** depicts a comparison of curve fitting method on the body curvature functions. The curve is fitted with non-linear Fourier series regression to minimize the influence of points far from the fitted line, and we have used Bisquare remain robust in regression. The bisquare weighting method minimizes a weighted sum of squares, where the weight given to each data point depends on how far the point is from the fitted line. As we might get some points away from the fitted curve which could be caused by inaccuracy of the post-processing, we chose the method to avoid influences from those points to fit the curve most relevant to the real condition.

$$\arctan\left(\frac{y_{i+2} - y_{i+1}}{x_{i+2} - x_{i+1}}\right) - \arctan\left(\frac{y_{i+1} - y_i}{x_{i+1} - x_i}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$a \cos(\omega t) + b \sin(\omega t) \quad (2)$$

Table 4. Detailed orientation angles for the entire fish body

Time (s)	A2(rad)	A3(rad)	A4(rad)	A5(rad)	A6(rad)	A7(rad)	A8(rad)
0	-0.1069	-0.1073	-0.1578	-0.1926	-0.4647	-0.195	-0.2018
0.0033	0.1087	0.1127	-0.4663	-0.4209	-0.2655	-0.454	-0.571
0.0067	0.3033	0.3623	-0.1431	-0.1473	0.1677	0.1059	0.2366
0.0100	-0.0867	-0.0702	0.144	0.1294	0.4787	0.4812	0.5591
0.0133	-0.3315	-0.3929	0.443	0.4026	0.1142	0.2005	0.1966
0.0167	-0.1113	-0.1294	-0.1681	-0.1644	-0.4316	-0.2033	-0.1404
0.0200	0.1131	0.1246	-0.4638	-0.4562	-0.2027	-0.5499	-0.4805
0.0233	0.3254	0.3369	-0.1696	-0.1213	0.155	0.1684	0.1053

0.0267	-0.1019	-0.1213	0.1298	0.199	0.4377	0.4719	0.4889
0.0300	-0.3504	-0.3506	0.4579	0.455	0.1845	0.1537	0.1156
0.0333	-0.131	-0.1181	-0.158	-0.1209	-0.4936	-0.0724	-0.1005

Figure 30. Mechanisms of processing zebrafish swimming video. (A) Real zebrafish larvae transparent body (B) Key steps on getting a central line of zebrafish and equal-distant division of the central line (C) Mathematical expressions of relative intersection angle between each two segments of the fish body (D) Analytical expressions of relative orientation between each two segments

Table 5. Sample relative orientation functions along fish body

Relative orientation between two segments (rad)	Function
θ_1	0
θ_2	$-0.1735\cos 2\pi ft - 0.07855\sin 2\pi ft$
θ_3	$-0.1642\cos 2\pi ft - 0.1909\sin 2\pi ft$
θ_4	$-0.114\cos 2\pi ft - 0.154\sin 2\pi ft$
θ_5	$0.2965\cos 2\pi ft - 0.04858\sin 2\pi ft$
θ_6	$0.2523\cos 2\pi ft - 0.12415\sin 2\pi ft$
θ_7	$0.2748\cos 2\pi ft - 0.04349\sin 2\pi ft$
θ_8	$0.1954\cos 2\pi ft - 0.3002\sin 2\pi ft$
Span-wise length (mm)	0.4

3.2 FSI interaction simulation with *OpenFOAM*

As described at the beginning of the chapter, the simulation of the zebrafish larvae motion can be categorized as an FSI (fluid-structure interaction) problem, involving prescribed solid body deformation-induced self-propelled forward motion and resultant surrounding fluid effects. Details will be presented in the following sections.

3.2.1 Zebrafish larva CFD model

Zebrafish larva model used in *OpenFOAM* was built with 51 ellipses extracted from the real fish silhouette and controlled by nine deformation equations. The fish model is shown in **Fig. 31A**. Each ellipse is specified with chord length and height. To simplify the model, the eyes and fin fold are not included in the model. The final CFD model is shown with top and side view of zebrafish larvae in **Fig. 31B**, the continuous fish body, will be divided into several continuous segments to mimic the muscle contributions along the fish body, as shown in **Fig. 31C**. The body segments are

shown as blocks with different colours. In all our case, the entire fish body is divided into nine sections, and the influences on the number of segmentation will be discussed in the results. Details of the segmentation will be explained in the following article regarding multibody dynamics toolbox MBDyn (<https://www.mbdyn.org/>). The density of the fish is assumed to be the same as water, which is 1kg/m^3 , averaged body parameters such as body segments' mass and length listed in Table 6 are used for all fish in the CFD simulation.

The flow field was numerically simulated using the open-source CFD toolbox *OpenFOAM* version 3.0.x. The 3-D computational domain is 20 times the fish body length in the longitudinal (x) direction, ten times of fish body length in transverse (y) direction and four times of fish body length in perpendicular (z) direction as shown in **Fig. 33**. The overall fluid domain is assumed to be at rest initially, which means there is no incoming flow. In the simulation, the medium is water. Therefore, the kinematic viscosity of the fluid is $10^{-6}\text{m}^2/\text{s}$. Pressure boundary conditions are taken as zero gradient for all boundaries except the front and backplane, which are set as symmetry, velocity boundary conditions for the fish model were considered as '*movingWallVelocity*' for all body segments and fixed value for the remaining patches to mimic the physical environment of the experiment (Petri dish). The *movingWallVelocity* is a particular boundary condition applied in *OpenFOAM*, and it is used for moving mesh cases and sets the velocity to the desired value for moving walls. Local mesh around the fish body was depicted in **Fig. 32**, and the head region is enlarged to be more explicit. In our case, the entire domain consists of unstructured mesh only to tolerate large internal mesh deformation during self-propelled forward motion of the fish model. For ellipses with high aspect ratio at the tail region, the mesh is specially refined to ensure that enough cells are present to precisely capture the vortex detached at the tail tip. Also, we have built a particular region behind the fish to keep cell density lower than other regions to increase the mesh resolution and reduce total cell number (shown in **Fig. 33**). Reynolds number is defined as $\frac{vL}{\nu}$, v

stands for forward swimming velocity, L is the body length of fish larva, and ν represents the kinematic viscosity mentioned above. For the entire simulation, Reynolds number is estimated to be 300 according to the desired forward velocity of zebrafish larvae, which stands for intermediate flow regime, this is in consistent with the real fluid property of zebrafish larvae.

Figure 31. CFD model of zebrafish larvae. (A) Mathematical model of the fish larvae including 51 ellipses assigned with real fish larvae body length and width (B) Rendered CFD model for zebrafish larvae shown as top view (top) and side view (bottom) (C) Expression of segmentation along fish body

Table 6. Mass and length for each body segment numbered from 1 to 9

Body section number	Mass (mg)	Length (mm)
1	0.0385	0.4
2	0.0553	0.4
3	0.0425	0.48
4	0.0308	0.48
5	0.0212	0.48
6	0.019	0.48
7	0.011	0.48
8	0.009	0.48
9	0.003	0.32
Total	0.23	4

Figure 32. Mesh around fish body. The head region is enlarged to see more explicit unstructured mesh formation

Figure 33. Fluid domain of zebrafish larva and mesh refinement behind zebrafish body with a yellow color column

3.2.2 Solid zebrafish larvae body kinematics

As described above the FSI forward motion simulation involves two parts. The solid-body kinematics are solved by *MBDyn*, which is a multibody dynamics analysis software used as a general tool to address multidisciplinary simulation of multibody system, including rigid and flexible bodies subject to kinematic constraints. This software can solve the initial value problem in the form of Differential-Algebraic

Equations (DAE), integrated in time domain using A/L-stable multistep integration schemes (Li, 2014). Constraints can be added independently in *MBDyn*, both for rigid and flexible body with six degrees of freedom.

To mimic the vertebrate muscle structure of zebrafish larvae, we have built a continuous multi-segments fish model, which consists of several rigid body segments, it is convenient to use *MBDyn* to add multiple constraint equations to control the body deformation. A schematic diagram for the zebrafish model is displayed in **Fig. 34**. In *MBDyn*, Body's position and orientation are expressed by a particular unit '*node*', and this unit has six degrees of freedom. It contains position and orientation information shown as a black point in the figure. Constraint is expressed by another unit '*joint*' shown in **Fig. 34**, it can connect nodes and may have internal degrees of freedom (the reaction force). Depending on the types of *joint*, functions are different. For instance, spherical joint acts like a sphere between the two nodes and constrains the relative position but frees the relative orientation. Dashed lines between nodes and joint indicate that distance between node and joint can be variable or even coincident. Both of them can be expressed globally and locally, and we can also set up the initial position and orientation of the *node* and *joint* with a reference frame to simplify the relationships among those elements. An example of the initial node and joint setup is shown below with two pieces of code snippets:

```
structural: Node_body4, dynamic,  
           reference, Ref_Link3, null, (position)  
           reference, Ref_Link3, eye, (orientation)  
           reference, Ref_Link3, 0., 8.6125*0.00048, 0., (linear  
velocity)  
           0., 0., 17.5375; (angular velocity)
```

```

driven: 5, string, "Time > 0.016",
      joint: JoArT_body2_body3,
            axial rotation,
            Node_body2,
              reference, Ref_Link2, null,
              hinge, reference, Ref_Link2, eye,
            Node_body3,
              reference, Ref_Link2, null,
              hinge, reference, Ref_Link2, eye,
            string, "-0.1378*451.6*sin(451.6*Time)+
0.1435*451.6*cos(451.6*Time)"; (constraint equation)

```

The first snippet shows how a node is defined with the reference frame. Initialization of node requires four parameters, position, orientation, linear velocity and angular velocity. The second snippet introduces the joint information specified by two adjacent nodes. The first line specifies that the joint constraint is only active after 0.016 sec. The constrain is expressed with equation in the last line. In the example. The spatial location of the joint coincides with the two adjacent nodes. DAE of the two adjacent nodes are written in the form of Newton-Euler equations, constrained by Lagrange's multipliers λ :

$$\begin{aligned}
M(\mathbf{x})\dot{\mathbf{x}} &= \mathbf{q} \\
\dot{\mathbf{q}} + \Phi_{/\mathbf{x}}^T \lambda &= \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, \dot{\mathbf{x}}, t) \\
\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t) &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Where \mathbf{x} summarizes the n coordinates of the system, $M(\mathbf{x})$ is the mass matrix, \mathbf{q} summarizes the momentum and momenta moments, and \mathbf{f} summarizes the generic force including pressure and viscous force. In the example, two nodes are constrained with a Fourier's series equation. The DAEs are integrated with implicit A/L stable linear multistep integration schemes, and a prediction-correction approach is used (Masarati et al., 2014). In our current case, each body segment is represented by one node in *MBDyn*. Except the ground node is set as 'static' type, all of the body nodes are dynamic type, and each two adjacent nodes are constrained by a deformation equation fitted with MatLab curve-fitting toolbox.

Figure 34. Schematic diagram for fish model in MBDyn. A 3-D zebrafish model is shown in the left picture, indicating the expressions of position and orientation of the node, which represents the fish body. The relationship between node and joint is shown in the right figure, and the dashed line suggests that the position of node and joint can be coincident and the orientation can be different depending on the reference frame selected.

3.2.3 Hydrodynamic solver

As we intend to simulate the forward fish motion with prescribed deformation equation inside an immovable domain, we are focusing on dealing with dynamic internal mesh motion around the zebrafish model. In *OpenFOAM*, *PimpleDyMFoam* solver is used to solve the transient, incompressible and single-phase Newtonian fluids. It is a combination of *SIMPLE* and *PISO* algorithm to address pressure-velocity coupling (Liu et al., 2017). The incompressible conservation equations for mass and momentum are written in Eqn 2 by deriving the general governing equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho \phi = \underbrace{-\nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{U} \phi)}_{\text{Convection}} + \underbrace{\nabla \cdot (D \nabla \phi)}_{\text{Diffusive transport}} + \underbrace{S_\phi}_{\text{Source terms}}$$

Time accumulation

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{U} = 0 \tag{2}$$

$$\frac{\partial \vec{U}}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\vec{U} \otimes \vec{U}) + \nabla \cdot (\nu \nabla \vec{U}) - \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p$$

The first equation is the general governing equation. As the mass is not transferred by diffusion and there is no source term, by substituting ϕ with 1, we can get the mass conservation equation. As the transport of momentum is determined by shear rate tensor ν , and the source terms are pressure force if we neglect the gravitational acceleration, by substituting ϕ with \vec{U} and replace the shear rate tensor based on Laplace Equation, we can get the momentum conservation equation.

In the momentum conservation equation, time derivatives uses 2nd order implicit discretization scheme: CrankNicolson, and the pressure source term uses cell-limited Gauss interpolation scheme to limit interpolated face values to improve boundedness and stability. Diffusion of transport uses Gauss linear for interpolation of the diffusivity, and the convection term applies reconCentral interpolation scheme. In OpenFOAM, velocity is stored at the cell centre, and values need to be interpolated to the face centres linearly. ReconCentral interpolates the value in a different way that uses extrapolated gradient-based correction from both sides onto the face, using 1/2 weighting to increase stability for large deformation.

Zebrafish larva swim extremely fast with high tail beat frequency and amplitude, to mimic the forward motion of zebrafish larvae, the CFD solver needs to have both acceptable accuracy and high stability, and the internal mesh motion needs to be appropriately maintained.

To keep the accuracy and stability of our results, we have made following modifications for discretization schemes and equation solvers

- 2nd order discretization scheme for time derivative
- Strong Coupling between *OpenFOAM* and *MBDyn*, i.e. inner iterations within a one-time step
- *ReconCentral* interpolation scheme for velocity
- Minimal relaxation factor for pressure
- BiCGStab solver for velocity equation

3.2.4 Coupling Strategy

Coupling between *OpenFOAM* and *MBDyn* is achieved using communication primitives provided by *MBDyn*. To satisfy convergence criteria, a strong coupling, which enables multistep interactions at each time step, is used between the two software. The schematic diagram for fluid and zebrafish larva motion coupling is shown in **Fig. 35**. As indicated in the image, kinematic data, i.e., position and orientations of nodes in *MBDyn*, are transmitted bi-directionally. Inter-process communication is built with Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) socket. An external force element in *MBDyn* allows to communicate positions and orientations of a set of nodes, and the corresponding linear and angular velocities with *OpenFOAM*. Within one time step, the above data can be transmitted either in the global frame or in the reference frame. On the other side, once *OpenFOAM* has received kinematic information, the information will be stored in the Centre of rotation (CoR) of each body, forces and moments are calculated based on the updated positions and orientations of current and previous time step implicitly and transmitted back to *MBDyn*. *MBDyn* will receive these data and update to the new locations and directions. Once the convergence criteria set in *OpenFOAM* are satisfied, the transmission comes to an end and jump to the next time step. Detailed explanations on the communication will be shown in the following paragraph.

Figure 35. Data transmission flow chart between *OpenFOAM* and *MBDyn*

As mention above, after *OpenFOAM* received a set of nodes' information on new time step from *MBDyn*, positions and orientations will be assigned to CoR of each body and all of the surface points' spatial location will be updated according to the CoR displacement during one time-step. The fish body consists of several connected segments, and there exists relative orientation between each two segments, surface meshes in the middle region need to be dealt with appropriately; otherwise, the internal mesh quality around body surface cannot be guaranteed. A schematic diagram depicting the relationship between each two segments is shown in **Fig. 36**. (To express the weighting method more comfortable, we use 2-D rectangles to represent the fish body segments). Initial state of the two segments is shown in Fig. 8A, points A and B represent the CoR of body segments. To avoid consequences shown in Fig. 8B, we have introduced a weighting method to smooth variations in the middle region.

For an arbitrary point i on body one surface (including intersection point of two segments), instead of following CoR of Body 1, the kinematic information is provided by both point A and point B. Assuming that P stores the position and orientation information of an arbitrary point on body one surface, it should be equal to the reference $P_i = P_A$ if we only consider the influence on point i from point A. as the spatial displacement of point A cannot be the same as point B, a surface point close to the middle region will have a same spatial location but different coordinates. The new weighting method specifies the surface point i information with the following equation:

$P_i = (1 - \omega)P_A + \omega P_B$, ω is the weighted parameter represented by the distance between point i and point A relative to the distance between point A and point B. the farther the surface point is to point A, the less influence point A has on surface deformation in the middle region, this is also reasonable on the intersection point of the two body segments, at this moment, ω equals 1, and the surface point is fully controlled by point B.

A

B

Figure 36. Schematic diagram of the relationship between two segments. (A) Initial state of the two segments, points A and B represent CoR of the two body, point i is an arbitrary point on the body surface. (B) Overlap in the middle region of the two segments after relative orientations. Area in the green circle will lead to terrible mesh quality.

4. Results and Discussions

The methodology we have developed needs to be validated. We have divided the validation process into two steps, the first step is the validation of numerical coupling of OpenFOAM and MBDyn, and the second part is the validation of the simulation based on real data observed from the experiment and post-processed with in-house MatLab code. The following sections will include the mandatory validations.

4.1 Validations on numerical methodology

The numerical methodology we have built include a strong coupling between OpenFOAM and MBDyn to solve the typical FSI interactions between a self-propelled zebrafish larva model and the surrounding water. To validate the methodology, we started from validations on multi-body structures. We have chosen a multi-body structure inspired by jellyfish provided by Wilson (Wilson and Eldredge, 2011). The author has extracted a multi-body model based on the real silhouette of jellyfish, which is depicted in **Fig. 37A**. The black dots indicates secants used to divide the centreline of jellyfish body and the body segments are expressed with mutually buoyant rigid elliptical bodies shown as **Fig. 37B**. In this figure, the relative angle between each two ellipses is prescribed from a sequence of snapshots of the outline of this jellyfish body over two contraction cycles. The captured values are depicted in **Fig. 37C** and is expressed with Eqn 1. Left-right symmetry was enforced for the structure and the prescribed kinematics, therefore, only half of the body information is required. By specifying relative orientation equations between each two segments, the jellyfish model can move upwards with alternant contraction and refilling. To scale the coordinates, an effective length L is defined as the arc length from the orifice lip to the inner most hinge (hinge 3). As shown in **Fig. 37B**, H and D denotes the height and diameter of the model, respectively. Based on the two parameters, during contraction and refilling movements, additional two length scales

are defined: the mean height of the bell \bar{H} , where $\bar{H} / L \approx 0.67$, and the maximum diameter of the bell, D_{\max} , where $D_{\max} / L \approx 2.1$. As our case for zebrafish forward swimming does not include passive joint, in the validation we have selected fully prescribed constraints on hinges with kinematic Reynolds number equivalent to 140 for comparison. The definition of Reynolds number is a bit different, which is based on the prescribed hinge kinematics including the maximum diameter and undulation period, expressed as $\frac{D_{\max}^2}{T\nu}$, where ν is the fluid kinematic viscosity. In

OpenFOAM, mesh around jellyfish model was fully unstructured depicted in **Fig. 37D**. As the jellyfish model is two dimensional, the length in z direction is set as 1.

We first compared kinematic performance of jellyfish motion including the longitudinal centroid position and velocity. Here, both of the parameters are non-dimensionalized with the average height, expressed as $\frac{Y_c}{\bar{H}}$ and $\frac{V_c T}{\bar{H}}$, respectively.

As shown in **Fig. 38A**, the longitudinal centroid position of jellyfish is moving upwards as time evolves, and the longitudinal centroid velocity is gradually increasing towards a constant state after approximately four periods of time (shown as **Fig. 38B**). Both of the comparisons are slightly different from the past studies, this are most likely to be caused by the different hinge kinematics extracted from the scattered points depicted in **Fig. 38C**. Depending on various curve fitting toolbox and methods, the fitted sinusoidal function can be slightly different. Unfortunately we have not acquired the data used by the author.

Besides, we compared the required input hinge power, which mimics the muscle power provided by relative angle orientation function applied on hinges to power jellyfish's upward motion. Power required to activate hinges should be equal to the sum of power resulting from the rate of change of kinetic energy of the system of bodies and rate of change of energy stored and released as they are deflected minus

the work done by the fluid to the system of bodies, which is $W_h = \dot{E}_s + \dot{E}_b - \dot{W}_f$. The deflecting power is calculated with the sum of power of all the hinges, which is

$$\dot{E}_s = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} k_i (\theta_i - \theta_{e_i}) \dot{\theta}_i, \text{ n-1 is the number of hinges and } k_i \text{ is the stiffness of hinge}$$

i. The power of the system of bodies is calculated with $\dot{E}_b = \sum_{i=1}^n (A_i (\dot{x}_i \cdot \ddot{x}_i) + J_i \dot{\alpha}_i \ddot{\alpha}_i)$,

where A_i is the area of body i and J_i is the polar moment of inertia of body i. **Fig.**

38C depicts the comparison of required input power of hinges between validation paper and our simulated results. It can be seen from the figure that our curve matches well with the previous result. In addition, a comparison of vorticity at 140 Reynolds number has been made (depicted in **Fig. 38D**).

$$\theta_1 = -0.1472 \cos(6.538t) - 0.3247 \sin(6.538t) + 0.7551$$

$$\theta_2 = -0.2366 \cos(6.456t) + 0.1645 \sin(6.456t) + 0.3472$$

(1)

$$\theta_3 = -0.08218 \cos(6.427t) + 0.04095 \sin(6.427t) + 0.4511$$

Figure 37. (A) Extracted jellyfish body model from real outline. (B) Divided jellyfish body expressed with mutually buoyant ellipses. (C) Fitted sinusoidal curves representing relative orientations of two adjacent ellipses based on jellyfish contraction and refilling motion. (D) Jellyfish model in OpenFOAM (Wilson and Eldredge, 2011)

Figure 38. Kinematic and dynamic results comparisons between current simulation and validation paper. (A) Longitudinal centroid position (B) longitudinal centroid velocity (C) Required input power (D) vorticity contour comparison with Wilson & Eldredge's results

4.2 Zebrafish larvae forward motion validation

4.2.1 Validation on forward motion kinematics

To validate whether our numerical methodology could simulate the real forward motion of zebrafish larvae, we are going to compare the kinematic performance of zebrafish larvae model with the real fish locomotion observed with high speed camera. The zebrafish larvae body deformation equation is obtained as an input for OpenFOAM solver and the equations we have used is shown in Table 7. In this case, the fish larva generated a body wave travelling down its body at a near constant rate, therefore, frequency for each equation is assumed to be constant. The real zebrafish larvae forward velocity is calculated with the changing positions of centre of mass obtained from MatLab post-processing toolbox, and fitted to a sinusoidal curve. As the equations can only specify the relative orientations of two adjacent body segments, the angle variation of the first (head) and last (tail) body segments are not prescribed, therefore, we compared the head and tail angle first between experiments and numerical simulation. In **Fig. 39(A-B)**, the black curve indicates the simulated head and tail angle, as the fish is moving cyclically, the resulting head and tail angle values should evolve like a sinusoidal curve with time. The captured head and tail angle data (shown as red dot) at some specific frames from the recorded video supported the result, showing that the experimental data fit well with the simulated angle curve.

Table 7. Zebrafish larvae body deformation equations

Relative orientation between two segments (rad)	Function $2\pi f = 397.9$
θ_1	0
θ_2	$-0.1465\cos 2\pi ft + 0.1346\sin 2\pi ft$
θ_3	$-0.1245\cos 2\pi ft + 0.1327\sin 2\pi ft$
θ_4	$-0.1542\cos 2\pi ft + 0.1294\sin 2\pi ft$
θ_5	$0.1565\cos 2\pi ft + 0.2264\sin 2\pi ft$
θ_6	$0.1723\cos 2\pi ft + 0.2724\sin 2\pi ft$
θ_7	$0.2123\cos 2\pi ft + 0.184\sin 2\pi ft$
θ_8	$0.2458\cos 2\pi ft + 0.2673\sin 2\pi ft$
Span-wise length (mm)	0.4

In **Fig. 39C**, we depicted 8 midlines of zebrafish larvae for approximately two tail beat cycles. The midlines were extracted from binary images selected with relatively large tail beat amplitudes. X and Y coordinates are normalized with fish body length to express the distance travelled more straightforward. As can be seen from the figure, the fish is moving forward almost parallel to X axis (with a slight angle deviation less than 15 degree). In the anterior part of the curve (approximately 20%), the bending is not significant, supporting the assumption that the anterior part is too stiff to undergo bending, expressed as zero relative orientation between the first two segments shown in Table 7. **Fig. 39D** showed comparisons of forward velocity. In OpenFOAM, the forward velocity is calculated with the centre of mass (COM) of simulated fish model. As shown in Eqn 2a, the position vector P_{COM} was calculated by dividing the sum of the product of each body segment m_i and position vector P_i with total fish body mass m_{body} . The simulated zebrafish model forward swimming speed is approximately $17.25l_{body} / s$, and the experimentally observed speed is about $19l_{body} / s$. The slight different between experiment and CFD simulation on forward velocity which is about

10%, can be caused by the slight discrepancies in morphology. Also, insufficient accuracy of the fish midline extraction might lead to slight inconsistency in certain captured points along the body, and this could influence the Fourier series curve fitting, or most likely, due to the fact that the real fish changes its body wave shape instantly during each tail beat cycle, leading to small changes in swimming speed, which will not occur in the prescribed cyclic swimming of the CFD fish model (Li et al., 2012). To make the swimming speed value more persuasive, we have also collected the simulated results for ten zebrafish larvae and made comparisons in **Fig. 39E**. Besides, from **Fig. 39C**, it is also possible to estimate the experimentally observed swimming speed to be around $19l_{body} / s$.

$$P_{COM} = \frac{\sum m_i P_i}{m_{body}} \quad (2)$$

Figure 39. Comparison results between experiments and CFD simulation. (A) Head angle (B) Tail angle (C) Zebrafish midline for two full tail beat cycles derived from high speed video of 500 fps (E) Velocity comparison for 10 different zebrafish larvae

Zebrafish larvae tends to swim in an intermediate flow regime with Reynolds number ranging from 10 to 1000, and it has been studied that larvae fish always require higher Strouhal number than adult fish (Borazjani and Sotiropoulos, 2008). To validate our simulation, we calculated the Strouhal number for simulated CFD results. The Strouhal number (St) is a dimensionless number describing oscillating flow

mechanisms and is defined as $\frac{Af}{U}$ in swimming animals, where A is the tail beat

peak-to-peak amplitude, f is the tail beat frequency and U is the averaged swimming velocity. In our simulation, the Strouhal number is approximately 0.8. Considering the desired Reynolds number, our result is in reasonable range between 0.69 and 1.07 stated in Li's paper (Li et al., 2016), suggesting that our simulation meets the requirements of a real zebrafish larvae. Besides, we have compared the gestures of fish swimming between CFD simulated motions and experimentally observed motion, together with the detached vortices in **Fig. 40**. **Fig. 40** depicts the vorticity iso-surfaces formed based on Q Criterion behind a swimming normal zebrafish larva at different instants in time within one time period and the dorsal view for vorticity iso-surfaces. Here, Q can describe the wake topology and defines vortices as positive second invariant of velocity gradient in region where vorticity magnitude is greater than strain-rate magnitude (Kolář, 2007). As seen from the most left and right column of **Fig. 40**, flow patterns behind the fish are represented by detached vortices and shown as translucent green fragments. Vortices starts to form in the vicinity of head, transmits downstream to tail and detaches at the tail, which are consistent with the fish tail motion; when the lateral displacement of the tail reaches the highest amplitude, vortices starts to shed at the tail tip, the already formed vorticity in the wake are mixed with the newly formed vorticity at tail tip. The most right column also displays a 3-D view of the vortex rings generated behind the fish to understand formation of flow patterns better. To validate the numerical methodology, **Fig. 40** also compares the body curvatures of CFD model and the real fish in the recorded experiment video. As can be seen, two sets of results match very well in terms of body shape at all specific time within a period, indicating that our CFD model is able to imitate the self-propelled swimming of zebrafish larva and its interactions with surrounding fluid.

X-Y plane vorticity	Experiment	Q
A		
B		
C		
D		

Figure 40. Vortex rings behind zebrafish larva for $Q=0.5$ at different time step within one period of time and the corresponding video record for the experiment. X-Y plane vorticity is a 2-D view of the 3-D vortices which can compare the body curvature with experiment results easier. From A-D, E-H and I-L, time steps are 0, $T/3$, $2T/3$ and T for each column. T represents one period of time.

4.2.2 Grid independence & Sensitivity test

Under the consideration of economic cost in calculation, a grid independence test is necessary to be carried out on a self-propelled zebrafish with fully prescribed deformation under two mesh sizes, medium and fine mesh. In addition, the time step influence is also tested, e.g. Case 1: Medium mesh (M) with 83200 total cells and time step of $T/650$, Case 2: Medium mesh & smaller time step (MS) of 83200 cells and time step of $T/1300$, and Case 3: Fine mesh (F) of 166400 cells and time step of $T/650$. The size of the fluid domain remains same for three cases.

To exclude mesh resolution and time step size influences on simulation results, we have compared the forward velocity and total force of zebrafish larvae in E3 medium and the results are shown in **Fig. 41(A-B)**. Computational results for three cases including kinematic performance and fluid domain calculation shows close results. To save computational time and keep accuracy, we use the mesh format and time step size the same as Case 1 for the entire following calculation.

In addition, we have also tested the sensitivity of the results to body segments of zebrafish larvae model with CFD simulation. Considering the accuracy and efficiency for body segmentation, we have divided the body trunk into 5, 10 and 15 segments, respectively. By capturing the body deformation and simulate the forward motion with CFD toolbox, we compared the forward velocity and total hydrodynamic force in

Figure 41. Grid independence test with acetic acid treated zebrafish larva sensitivity study. (A) Forward velocity for three levels of grid. (B) Total force in the moving direction for three levels of grid. (C) Forward velocity for three numbers of segmentations. (D) Total hydrodynamic force for three numbers of segmentations.

4.3. Comparisons of kinematic and energetics before and after drug treatment

4.3.1 Comparisons before and after 0.01% acetic acid due to nociceptive responses

Nociception study on fish is becoming more and more dominant in the current research field. As acetic acid has been validated to be able to trigger nociceptive responses, we intend to study kinematic and dynamic performance of zebrafish larvae under 0.01% acetic acid induced nociceptive responses. Detailed experimental setup has been stated in the methodology chapter, here we will focus on the numerical simulation results.

We first studied the influence of kinematic performance of 5 dpf zebrafish larvae. Extracted body curvature equations after acid treatment have higher averaged frequency compared with those of control group. This is quite reasonable as acetic acid treated zebrafish might accelerate quicker to reach the maximum speed and escape the acid environment (Lopez-Luna et al., 2017a). As depicted in **Fig. 42**, head and tail angle and forward velocity have been compared respectively before and after 0.01% acetic acid treatment. There is a slight increase in maximum tail beat angle after treated with acetic acid, but the head turning angle does not show any significant changes. This might be due to the assumption that the anterior part of zebrafish larvae (approximately 20% of body length) behaves more stiff than the other part, therefore, the changes of head region curvature due to nociceptive stimuli might not be as obvious as the tail region. Considering the tail beat angle, there is an approximately 7 degrees' of variation before and after acid treatment. The value cannot be regarded as significant, whereas considering the forward velocity, the increment is much more significant, which suggests that to reach higher speeds, increasing tail beat frequency would be more effective than increasing tail beat amplitude. This assumption has already been studied by other researchers with similar conclusions (Borazjani and Sotiropoulos, 2009, Muller, 2004). Muller added new ideas based on his research on

different ages' zebrafish larvae (van Leeuwen et al., 2015), suggesting that for younger larvae, tail beat frequency is the primary method to reach higher speeds, whereas for older zebrafish larvae, both frequency and amplitude contribute to the increase of forward velocity. This is quite reasonable as our simulation reveals that both frequency and tail beat amplitude have increased resulting higher forward speed.

Figure 42. Kinematic performance before and after 0.01% acetic acid treatment. (A) Head and tail angle comparison (B) Forward velocity comparison during cyclic swimming, the image did not include the startle stage

Compared to kinematic characteristics, dynamic performance including force and power is not that straightforward as it can be hardly acquired with direct observations or camera recordings. In this chapter, we will start with hydrodynamic and mechanical power consumption during self-propelled forward motion. As the movement of each two neighbouring body segments is constrained with a prescribed deformation equation except for fish head and tail, mechanical power contribution along fish body can be approximated by power generated by virtual joint between each two body segments. During muscle contraction, fish body bends, energy is generated and transmitted into the water, and the bended body interacts with the surrounding fluid, a thrust force generates and pushes the fish moving forward. Within this process, Approximately 20% of the energy (depending on fish species, the percentage can float dramatically) (Zhang et al., 2014) generated by muscle contraction is consumed due to the viscous dissipation of fish body tissues, and the remaining energy is transmitted into the water. In our model, viscous dissipations of fish body

tissues are neglected to simplify the simulation. During cyclic swimming, as a continuous fish body, the total kinetic energy expressed as Eqn 3(a) is zero, therefore, all the effective mechanical energy generated by fish muscle is used to balance the external energy (shown as Eqn 3(b-c)). The mechanical power generated from fish muscle includes the translational power due to linear motion and the rotational power due to body rotation, in this case, all the other terms are cancelled out except for the rotational power. Therefore, the mechanical power is estimated with the cross product of torque and angular velocity expressed with Eqn 3(d), and the total power transmitted into the water is expressed with Eqn 3(e).

$$W_{internal(fish_to_fish)} + W_{external(fluids_to_fish)} = \Delta E_{fish_kinetic} = 0 \quad 3(a)$$

$$W_{internal(fish_to_fish)} = -W_{external(fluids_to_fish)} \quad 3(b)$$

$$P_{internal(fish_to_fish)} = -P_{external(fluids_to_fish)} \quad 3(c)$$

$$P_{internal(fish_to_fish)} = \sum_i M_i \cdot \omega_i \quad 3(d)$$

$$P_{external(fluids_to_fish)} = \sum_j -F_j \cdot V_j - M_j \cdot \omega_j \quad 3(e)$$

In the above equations, $\Delta E_{fish_kinetic}$ represents total kinetic energy, mechanical energy and power are expressed with $W_{internal(fish_to_fish)}$ and

$P_{internal(fish_to_fish)}$, and fluid energy and power exerted on fish body are expressed with $W_{external(fluids_to_fish)}$ and $P_{external(fluids_to_fish)}$. M_i is the internal torque for the i^{th} joint calculated by MBDyn in the global frame, ω_i represents the angular velocity for the i^{th} joint. F_j is the hydrodynamic force acting on the j^{th} body and V_j is the velocity of j^{th} body. M_j and ω_j have similar meaning to M_i and ω_i , but the target is body segment instead of virtual joint.

Comparisons of averaged power between control group are shown in **Fig.43A**, as the absolute value of hydrodynamic power equals the mechanical power, we will only display hydrodynamic power comparison. Acetic acid treated zebrafish larvae group

generated higher power than control group, this is consistent with the velocity tendency as the power variation is correlated with force and velocity. A further comparison on hydrodynamic power against tail beat frequency of ten zebrafish larvae siblings is shown in **Fig. 43B**. We have also calculated the cost of transport for two groups' of zebrafish. The cost of transport is defined as energy spent to travel unit distance per unit mass, which is expressed as $\frac{P_m}{U}$, P_m is the power per unit mass, and U is the averaged forward velocity. The resulting values for cost of transport is $81.73\mu\text{J}/\text{m} \cdot \text{kg}$ and $96.24\mu\text{J}/\text{m} \cdot \text{kg}$ for control group and acetic acid treated group, respectively. These values are similar to those reported by Li et al (from $105\mu\text{J}/\text{m} \cdot \text{kg}$ to $50\mu\text{J}/\text{m} \cdot \text{kg}$) in (Li et al., 2016) on larvae zebrafish. The increment of speed and tail beat frequency in the intermediate flow regime ($10 < \text{Re} < 10^3$) increased the energy dissipation, resulting in higher cost of transport, which agrees with previous study (Li et al., 2012).

Figure 43. Hydrodynamic (A) and mechanical (B) power comparison between control group and 0.01% acetic acid treated group.

To further understand the different power generated at different locations along the fish body, we have also studied the kinematic and dynamic performance variations along fish body. Starting from regional analysis, we have selected three typical points (shown in **Fig. 44A**) along fish body to represent head region, middle region and tail region, respectively. Time history of force and velocity are compared and depicted in

Fig. 44(B-C). The trajectory is not completely parallel to x axis in global frame (about 15 degrees), therefore, force and velocity are pointing towards the real moving direction of zebrafish. A full body length distribution of forward component of body force is also depicted in **Fig. 44D**, as we have divided the body into nine consecutive segments, forces distributed along the body are expressed with nine discrete averaged values to represent hydrodynamic forces acting on each body segments. The force shows negative value from head to approximately 30% of body length (which is roughly anterior to centre of mass), suggesting net drag generation in this region. Posterior to COM, the force value is mainly positive except near zero (slightly negative) value at 60% of body length, indicating that the posterior part mainly generate thrust force to power the forward motion. However, as our fish model is not a flexible continuous body, the force distribution is only an approximation of averaged value. For example, force distribution around 60% of body length could be more complex instead of an averaged near zero value.

Figure 44. Velocity and force distribution along zebrafish body (A) Real zebrafish picture with three tested typical points along the body (B) Global velocity of the three points (C) Hydrodynamic force of the three points (D) Forward component of total force distribution along the body

Although the absolute value of averaged hydrodynamic power equals the mechanical power, the distribution along fish body might differ. Therefore, we have calculated the hydrodynamic and mechanical power distribution along the body in **Fig. 45**. A more detailed mechanical and hydrodynamic power and an approximation of cost of transport are summarised in Table 8. Based on our results the hydrodynamic power generation shows an increase starting from the centre of mass and a deep increase in the rear region starting from 75% of body length. According to motion equations, this region has the largest motion amplitude along the body in global frame, resulting in larger fluid force, thus more hydrodynamic power. Ideally, the consumption of muscle power requires a study of muscle strain and electromyography (EMG) patterns for muscle function at specific positions along the body. However, the extremely small body size of larval fish makes it impossible to place receivers on the body. Constraints added in our fish model provide energy to move forward from static state, which perform as muscle fibre in real fish to provide mechanical power. The examined mechanical power shows a steep increase towards the tail from the middle region and then a steep decrease in the tail region. This might suggest that the main power generated by muscle to support steady forward swimming exists in the entire body. The conclusion seems to be inconsistent with the previous viewpoint that most power is generated in the anterior region, while the posterior region performs like a transmitter. However, based on the equations set up in our model, the anterior region equations have smaller curvature, implying that the simulated muscle in this region has smaller strain when it is contracted, thus less positive work is done. Moreover, during steady swimming state, red muscle dominates the swimming motion, if the main muscle power is generated in the anterior part, loss of energy in the form of heat occurs in the process of force transmission towards the tail, which might increase the burden of red muscle as it powers the entire steady swimming process (Lawrence C.

Rome et al., 1993). Whereas given that muscle functions vary among different species, our results need to be further tested with the help of biological analysis.

Figure 45. Statistical analysis of hydrodynamic (A) and mechanical (B) power distribution along the body with mean \pm sd. .

Table 8. Detailed hydrodynamic and mechanical power of 10 fish and cost of transport

		S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	cost of transport μ J/m
fish1	Hyd	0.16	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.09	0.14	0.08	0.26	0.55	79.97
	Mec	0.00	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.21	0.32	0.38	0.31	0.07	
fish2	Hyd	0.17	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.08	0.12	0.08	0.26	0.51	78.78
	Mec	0.00	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.20	0.31	0.36	0.30	0.07	
fish3	Hyd	0.19	0.04	0.06	0.07	0.11	0.14	0.09	0.26	0.56	84.33
	Mec	0.00	0.03	0.05	0.09	0.21	0.32	0.41	0.33	0.08	
fish4	Hyd	0.23	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.12	0.15	0.10	0.08	0.63	90.57
	Mec	0.00	0.04	0.06	0.12	0.22	0.37	0.49	0.34	0.08	
fish5	Hyd	0.18	0.04	0.05	0.07	0.12	0.16	0.09	0.28	0.55	80.64
	Mec	0.00	0.04	0.06	0.09	0.21	0.31	0.42	0.33	0.08	
fish6	Hyd	0.19	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.14	0.09	0.28	0.54	77.61
	Mec	0.00	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.20	0.33	0.40	0.31	0.08	
fish7	Hyd	0.18	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.10	0.14	0.09	0.28	0.59	85.56
	Mec	0.00	0.04	0.06	0.09	0.22	0.31	0.42	0.33	0.10	
fish8	Hyd	0.18	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.10	0.13	0.09	0.27	0.55	79.66
	Mec	0.00	0.04	0.04	0.07	0.20	0.32	0.41	0.31	0.08	
fish9	Hyd	0.18	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.10	0.13	0.09	0.27	0.55	79.18
	Mec	0.00	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.21	0.32	0.42	0.30	0.08	
fish10	Hyd	0.18	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.10	0.12	0.09	0.28	0.61	81.01
	Mec	0.00	0.04	0.06	0.09	0.21	0.31	0.41	0.33	0.09	

In **Fig. 46**, we compares the vorticity on x-y plane of the 3-D fish model. By comparing them im one period of time, it can be seen that the vortex detached from the tail tip is faster for acid treated group compared with control group fish. The earlier detached vortex has been labelled with black circles in the right column, indicating larger distance travelled within one period of time, i.e., higher velocity. The vorticity results for control and acetic acid treated group are in consistent with velocity comparisons depicted in **Fig. 42B**.

Figure 46. Vorticity comparisons in x-y plane between control group zebrafish and drug treated groups within one period of time. For A-D. E-H, time steps are 0, T/3, 2T/3 and T for each column. T represents one period of time.

4.3.2 Comparisons before and after 500 μM diphenylhydantoin (DPH) and 100mg/L yohimbine solution (yohimbine hydrochloride) neuroactive drugs

Administration of neuroactive drugs is an effective method to test animal's nervous system functions (Irons et al., 2010). As neuroactive drugs acting on different neural pathways could cause different behavioural phenotypes, it is possible to study how the nervous system affects locomotion behaviours by applying different neuroactive drugs (Li et al., 2018). Zebrafish larva model was studied with same drugs used in adults and mammals and showed similar behavioural responses, suggesting that zebrafish larvae are sensitive to neuroactive drugs. Therefore, in the following part, we are going to present statistical analysis of the kinematic and dynamic performance variations before and after treatment of two commonly used neuroactive drugs, diphenylhydantoin (DPH) and yohimbine.

Compared to acetic acid, the two neuroactive drugs are more sensitive to concentrations and ages (Li et al., 2015, Zhao et al., 2020, Liu et al., 2016), different concentrations and lighting conditions can lead to reversed results for same drug. For instance, for 5 dpf zebrafish larvae, 10mg/L yohimbine will increase the locomotion activity of fish larvae, whereas 200mg/L yohimbine decreases the activity. In our study, we have selected two specific drug concentrations based on previous research to test the influences based on our 5 dpf zebrafish model. Similar kinematic and dynamic comparisons to acetic acid for neuroactive drugs are shown in **Fig. 47**.

Fig.47(A-B) depict the averaged head and tail comparison between control group and neuroactive drugs treated groups. As the drugs will influence swimming frequencies and initial angles, phase differences exist among those groups in head and tail angle, respectively. From those figures, there are no significant differences for the amplitude of head and tail angle, but only different tail beat frequencies. An illustration of forward swimming speed comparisons among control group and drug treated groups are presented in **Fig. 47C**. There is no significant differences between control group and 100mg/L yohimbine treated group, but the condition differs for 500 μM DPH

solution, and is manifested as a apparent decrease of velocity compared to control group. The results on velocity comparisons implies that the influences of neuroactive drugs on velocity could possibly be attributed to changes in tail beat frequency instead of tail beat amplitude.

Figure 47. Kinematic and dynamic performance comparisons of zebrafish larvae among control groups and neuroactive drugs treated groups. (A) Head angle (B) Tail angle (C) Forward velocity (D) Hydrodynamic power

We have also made statistical analysis on velocity and hydrodynamic power as it is more prudent to compare differences exist between control group and drug treated group. As shown in **Fig. 48**, the velocity and hydrodynamic relationship between control group and yohimbine treated group is ‘not significant’, implying that 100mg/L yohimbine does not have influences on zebrafish locomotion. Whereas such relationship behaves as ‘****’ between control group and DPH treated group, which suggests that there is a significant difference exists between results from control and 500 μM DPH groups. To justify 0.01% acetic acid influences, we have also added

acid group in the figure and the results complies with our previous findings. Finally, we compared the vorticity between control group neuroactive drugs treated group (shown as **Fig .49**). For DPH treated group, within same one period of time, the evolution of vorticity is much shorter than other groups, approximately half of other groups, suggesting that only half of the distance travelled by DPH treated group compared with control group. For yohimbine treated group, vorticity patterns are similar to those in control group. All of the vorticity results for drug treated groups are in consistent with velocity comparisons depicted in **Fig. 47**.

Figure 48. Statistical analysis on forward velocity (A) and hydrodynamic power (B) among control group and three types of drugs treated group with one-way ANOVA for totally twenty fish, expressed in mean \pm sd; for $P < 0.0001$ ****, ns represents not significant

Figure 49. Vorticity comparison among control group, yohimbine and DPH treated group. From A-D, E-H and I-L, time steps are 0, $T/3$, $2T/3$ and T for each column. T represents one period of time.

All of the aforementioned results related to acetic acid, yohimbine and DPH are similar to previous biological observations (Li et al., 2015, Liu et al., 2016), indicating that our method has the ability to replicate neuroactive drug influences on zebrafish larvae locomotion behaviours. The effect of exposure to acid on zebrafish swimming behaviour has been studied for different substances including acetic acid and citric acid at different zebrafish developmental stages (Lopez-Luna et al., 2017a, Nordgreen et al., 2014). However, these studies were limited to the nociceptive responses of zebrafish larvae on stress, fear or anxiety, i.e. environment influences. Furthermore, the observed data mainly focused on the total distance fish travelled in a period of time or the time spent in active status (Lopez-Luna et al., 2017b, Lopez-Luna et al., 2017a). To some extent, our developed tool can mimic the mutual interactions of real fish with the surrounding fluid and thus allows investigation of the

relationship between fish body mechanical force and torque and its swimming behaviours. Using this approach, our future work would focus on evaluating potential analgesic drugs for pain relief and neuroactive drug effects on fish behaviours, which might help to understand functions of nervous system.

4.4 Assistance of CFD simulation on the evaluation of Gypenoside protection in a zebrafish model

4.4.1 The effect of Gypenoside on swimming behaviour of zebrafish treated with acetic acid

Gypenosides has been shown to have a range of effects, including antioxidation, antilipidemia, neuroprotection and inflammation (Zhang et al., 2017). Although the possible protective effect of Gyp on zebrafish has been discussed on the oxidative stress associated with retinal degeneration (Alhasani et al., 2018), protection of Gyp against pain in zebrafish has been investigated only rarely. In the current study, we tested the protective action of Gyp against the toxic effects of 0.1% acetic acid by examining the effects of exposure to these substances on zebrafish larva locomotion and on the expression of ant-oxidative and proinflammatory genes.

Most studies involving the zebrafish pain model have focused on the effects of the surrounding fluid on kinematic and hydrodynamic performance but have failed to acknowledge the contribution of internal muscle mechanics. The locomotion of fish larvae is powered by an axial muscle system driven by motoneurons in the spinal cord (Voosenek et al., 2016b). Swimming kinematics are influenced by internal body mechanics and fluid mechanics (Eric.D.Tytell et al., 2010, McMillen and Holmes, 2006). Forces generated by muscle induce body deformation that in turn will change the fluid dynamics of the surrounding water, i.e., hydrodynamic force. This hydrodynamic force will then positively feedback to cause further changes in body

deformation (Voesenek et al., 2018a). This coupled mechanical interaction determines the motion of the fish through the water. Clearly, internal body mechanics are of significance in the study of body motion.

Swimming by fish larvae is powered by their axial muscle system (Voesenek et al., 2016b). For different fish species, the contribution of these muscles to swimming can vary. The power generated by muscle contraction bends the body and so interacts with the surrounding fluid. Muscle myotomes are aligned parallel to the longitudinal axis, with muscle fibers oriented about 40 degrees to the longitudinal axis of the fish (ALTRINGHAM and ELLERBY, 1999). Two types of muscles form the 3D structure on each side of the body. One type is white muscle, which powers the fish for fast starts such as escaping behaviors; the second type is red muscle that powers sustained swimming such as cyclic swimming (Ying Dou et al., 2008). During the larval stage, the white muscle is distributed predominantly in deeper regions below the skin and is enclosed in a thin outer layer of red muscle. Muscle contractions are driven by motoneurons in the spinal cord, and these contractions control the fish locomotion activity (Ekeberg and Lansne, 1995), therefore, muscle status can be reflected in activity level of the fish (Correia et al., 2011). We compared the time spent by each group in three different swimming conditions: Inactive (when the fish was at rest or showed only a subtle tail beat with no obvious displacement in the water), Active 1 (when the fish swam cyclically for a relatively long period of time) and Active 2 (when the fish was swimming for a short period of time including acceleration with large tail curvature followed by a quick de-acceleration). As shown in **Fig. 50A**, compared with control group, the Gyp-treated group did not show any obvious changes with regard to the percentage of time spent in active swimming, indicating that 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Gyp does not appear to be toxic to 5 dpf zebrafish larvae. Exposure to acetic acid resulted in the fish being inactive for 80% of the time. Inactivity decreased to approximately 50% of the time following Gyp treatment of fish exposed to acetic acid, suggesting an alleviatory effect of Gyp solution on the muscle inflammation caused by the acid. Cyclic swimming occurs randomly in 5 dpf zebrafish larvae (Muller, 2004); in the current study an increase of only 3% in time spent for cyclic

swimming was observed after Gyp treatment. However, for short time swimming, a significant increase of approximately 25% in total time is shown after GYP treatment, indicating increased enthusiasm. No obvious differences (less than 5% in total time) are apparent between the Gyp group and the Gyp+Acid group, suggesting that the Gyp solution has an alleviatory effect on the muscle inflammation caused by 0.1% acetic acid.

A

B

C

D

E

Figure 50. Comparisons of swimming status for each treatment group. AC: 0.1% acetic acid; GYP: Gypenosides Inactive (black column): Active 1: cyclic swimming (light grey) Active 2 (dark grey): short time swimming. (B) Velocity comparison for four groups. (C) Hydrodynamic power comparison for four groups. (D) Hydrodynamic power distribution along fish body. (E) Mechanical power distribution along fish body.

Based on the simulated results from *OpenFOAM* such as position and orientation for each segment, the forward velocity of the fish larva was calculated from center of mass (COM) of the fish body. The COM was derived from the position of each segment at each time step using a mass-averaged method (van Leeuwen et al., 2015). **Fig. 50B** shows a mean velocity comparison for all groups. The mean velocity of cruising in the acetic acid group was significantly lower than that in each of the other three groups, while the GYP+Acid group displayed a similar mean velocity to the Gyp and the control groups. The statistical analysis in **Fig. 51A** indicates that mean mean velocities of Gyp and GYP+Acid groups were significantly higher than that of the Acid group, suggesting that the effect on forward velocity of exposure to 0.1% acetic acid was alleviated by 5 µg/ml Gyp. **Fig. 50C** compares the hydrodynamic power of the control group with the drug-treated groups. It was not surprising that the tendency is similar to forward velocity as the hydrodynamic power was calculated based on the forward velocity of the fish. As we expected, 5 µg/ml Gyp could alleviate the influences on power generation, allowing the muscle of the zebrafish larvae to generate greater power, producing larger body deformation and larger hydrodynamic power compared with the 0.1% acetic acid treated group. The statistical analysis of hydrodynamic power shown in **Fig. 51B**. makes the conclusion more persuasive. There was a significant difference in hydrodynamic power before and after Gyp treatment with acetic acid; as the muscle correlated with the power supply, it was prudent to deduce that Gyp treatment could to some extent protect fish muscle from inflammation caused by acetic acid. Unlike many biomechanical situations in which the propulsive system is separate from the main body, zebrafish larvae undulated their entire body to swim forward (Zhao et al., 2018), therefore, the whole body contributes to generation of thrust and drag during the tail beat cycle,

although the contribution from each might differ. In **Fig. 50D** and **Fig. 50E**, we compared the distribution of hydrodynamic power and mechanical power along the fish body to quantify the differences of force and power for different groups. Given that the fish larvae were submerged in the solution, the whole body would have been exposed, therefore we assumed that the axial muscle along the entire body would be affected by exposure to acetic acid and Gyp. Although the total power is kept balanced during cruising, the power distribution is different for the internal muscle and body surface. The averaged hydrodynamic power for the fish larvae in different groups in **Fig. 50D** showed a significant higher value starting from approximately 75% of body length. According to motion equations, this region had the largest shape change along the body in global frame, resulting in larger fluid force and more hydrodynamic power. In **Fig. 50E**, the mechanical power generated along the body showed an increase towards the tail and a steep decrease at the tail. Higher mechanical power starts from approximately joint number 4, located at the centre of the body, indicating that the main power is generated in the posterior half of the body. In the posterior region, the larger body curvature indicates higher muscle strain, thus indicating that more strenuous work is done by this part of the body. Among the different groups, the group treated with 0.1% acetic acid displayed significantly lower hydrodynamic power and mechanical power. After treatment with Gyp, the power increased to a level close to that of the control group. For all body segments, both mechanical and hydrodynamic power followed the tendency of the total hydrodynamic power, suggesting that exposure influenced the entire axial muscle system. In this part of the study, the internal muscle power has been quantified to provide a better understanding of the beneficial effects of Gyp.

Figure 51. Statistical analysis for all tested groups on velocity (A) and Hydrodynamic power (B) with mean \pm s.d. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$. Control vs GYP is expressed with ‘#’ to represent significant differences between groups. Control vs Acid is expressed with ‘*’, and GYP+Acid vs Acid is expressed with ‘ Δ ’. The use of symbols is the same in subsequent images.

We also carried out statistical analysis of hydrodynamic and mechanical power at different body sections and virtual joints to clarify if the effects of Gyp protection varied along the zebrafish body (shown as **Fig. 52**). For hydrodynamic power, the overall tendency along the body of power generated remained the same with total body hydrodynamic power shown in **Fig. 51B**. It was obvious that the zebrafish larvae exposed to 0.1% acetic acid generated lower hydrodynamic power. When comparing Gyp and Gyp+Acid group, it is possible that at some body sections the Gyp+Acid group zebrafish can generate higher hydrodynamic power than that of Gyp group. This might be caused by minor side effects of Gyp, together with stimulation by acetic acid, as the effect of Gyp could vary at different body sections due to different organs and different absorbing abilities. However, similar circumstance should not affect mechanical power, which directly reflects power generated with muscle contractions.

Figure 52. Statistical analysis on hydrodynamic and mechanical power along the body. Body sections numbering from 1 to 9 depict hydrodynamic power comparisons among treated groups. Virtual joints numbering from 1 to 8 display mechanical power comparisons among treated groups. For all groups, ns, no significance; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$. Control vs GYP is expressed with ‘#’ to represent significant differences between groups. Control vs Acid is expressed with ‘*’, and GYP+Acid vs Acid is expressed with ‘Δ’.

4.4.2. Gypenoside increased anti-oxidative capacity and decreased inflammation in acetic acid-treated zebrafish larvae

Oxidative stress and inflammation play an important role in the development of pain (Keeble et al., 2009). Previous work showed that the natural product quercetin inhibited inflammatory pain by increasing glutathione (GSH) generation and decreasing the production of inflammatory mediators (Valério et al., 2009). Another natural product, diosgenin, demonstrated a capacity to ameliorate the neuropathic pain associated with diabetes mellitus. Diosgenin treatment in streptozotocin-induced

diabetic rat inhibited production of IL-1 β and TNF- α in serum, enhanced catalase and SOD activities in serum, sciatic nerve and dorsal root ganglion, and restored nociceptive thresholds (Kiasalari et al.). Our previous work demonstrated that Gyp restored antioxidative capacity and inhibited proinflammatory cytokine production in H₂O₂-treated retinal pigment epithelial (RPE) cells (Alhasani et al., 2018). In the present study we investigated whether Gyp mediated oxidative stress and inflammation in acetic acid-treated zebrafish larvae. QRT-PCR data demonstrated that expression of antioxidant genes, including SOD1, SOD2 and GPX1, was significantly decreased in acetic acid-treated zebrafish compared to untreated control zebrafish and that co-treatment with Gyp resulted in a marked increase in expression of these three genes (**Fig. 53A**). Acetic acid treatment caused significantly increased expression of inflammatory cytokine genes IL-1 β , IL-6 and TNF- α when compared to untreated control zebrafish; co-treatment with Gyp reversed the acetic acid-induced effects (**Fig. 53B**). Intraperitoneal injection of diluted acetic acid has been widely used to induce pain in rodent models (Ribeiro et al., 2000, Valério et al., 2009). Acetic acid induces production of inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β , IL-8 and TNF- α , which mediate writhing response in mice (Ribeiro et al., 2000). Acetic acid has been applied to induce pain and nociception in zebrafish (larvae or adults) via introduction to zebrafish water or by local injection (Lopez-Luna et al., 2017b, Lopez-Luna et al., 2017a, Steenbergen and Bardine, 2013, Taylor et al., 2017, Maximino, 2011, Schroeder and Sneddon, 2017). Studies on functional consequence of acetic acid exposure in zebrafish have mainly been focused on zebrafish locomotion activity and behaviour. Here we also examined effects of acetic acid on oxidative stress and inflammation in zebrafish (**Fig. 53**). Most importantly, we developed a novel approach to evaluate the therapeutic potential of Gyp for neuropathic pain.

Figure 53. Gyp regulated expression of antioxidant and proinflammatory genes. (A) Expression of antioxidant genes in untreated and treated zebrafish larvae. (B) Expression of proinflammatory genes. Experiments were repeated three times. Data were presented as means \pm standard error (SE). ns, no significance; * p <0.05, ** p <0.01, *** p <0.001. Control vs GYP is expressed with ‘#’ to represent significant differences between groups. Control vs Acid is expressed with ‘*’, and GYP+Acid vs Acid is expressed with ‘ Δ ’.

The above analysis of the protective effect of Gypenosides against 0.1% acetic acid on zebrafish larvae presented a new methodology to study zebrafish pain model. We have combined CFD simulations on zebrafish locomotion to study the effects on zebrafish behaviors and internal muscle mechanics. As a high concentration of acetic acid is known to cause pain/damage to zebrafish larvae muscle and has been tested extensively, we chose to investigate the protective effects of 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ Gyp against exposure to 0.1% acetic acid and observed the alleviation of muscle inflammation after Gyp treatment. The conclusions have been confirmed by both QRT-PCR data and CFD simulated results, showing that our computational method could assist in evaluating the protective effect of Gyp against acetic acid and other harmful substances. In addition, we have also quantified the internal muscle mechanics that can partially reflect the effects of medicine on muscle status, data that is difficult to acquire from standard experiments. Considering the cheaper cost and faster preparations of CFD simulation compared to QRT-PCR analysis, our method

could potentially be used to evaluate the effects of drugs on zebrafish behaviors and thus support the development of therapeutic drugs for neuropathic pain.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The work has introduced a novel methodology to quantify the drug influences on zebrafish larvae locomotion kinematics and energetics both experimentally and numerically. 5 dpf zebrafish larva was selected as a target for the drug treatment experiment. Drugs such as acetic acid, diphenylhydantoin (DPH), yohimbine and Gypenosides (GYP) have been selected to study influences of both analgesic and neuroactive drugs on zebrafish larvae locomotion, nociceptive induced responses, for example. The experiment was carried out with recordings of zebrafish larvae locomotion with the help of high speed camera, recorded videos will be post-processed with in-house MatLab code to extract the body deformation equations prepared for numerical simulation. The zebrafish larvae will be post-processed with total RNA isolation for the quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction (qRT-PCR). Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) software OpenFOAM were applied in the research to simulate the zebrafish locomotion, which is a typical fluid-structure interaction (FSI) case. OpenFOAM was coupled with a multibody dynamic software MBDyn to solve the FSI problem.

Numerical methodology was validated with past research articles about a jelly-fish like multibody structures and experiments. Kinematic performance of zebrafish larvae such as head and tail beat angle and forward velocity were compared with experimentally measured results, comparisons presented good quantitative agreement. Gestures of recorded real zebrafish larvae locomotion and simulated results were compared within one period of time to support this quantitative agreement.

Quantification of drug influences on fish larvae locomotion was carried out in two steps. The first step includes study of nociceptive and neuroactive drugs' influences on fish larvae locomotion. Reasonable comparison results have been supplied, 0.01% acetic acid has a positive influence on 5 dpf zebrafish locomotion, when it comes to

500 μM DPH, the influence turns into negative, and the 100mg/mL yohimbine did not bring any significant variations on swimming behaviors. Changes in kinematics have been supported by vorticity generation as well. Moreover, we estimated the Strouhal number value, which is approximately 0.8. The value is much higher than optimal streamlined fish swimming value of 0.5. This can be explained with the fact that zebrafish larvae swim in intermediate flow regime where viscous force dominant. Therefore, overcoming such viscous effect requires more thrust and thus higher Strouhal number is needed.

Different from previous researches related to drug influences on zebrafish larvae focusing more on kinematic behaviors, our study quantified the hydrodynamic performance and internal muscle mechanics. Based on our results, the hydrodynamic power generation shows an increase starting from the centre of mass and a steep increase in the rear region. Constraints added in our fish model provide energy to move forward from static state, which perform as muscle fibre in real fish to provide mechanical power. Mechanical power distribution shows a steep increase towards the tail from the middle region and then a steep decrease in the tail region. This might suggest that the main power generated by muscle to support steady forward swimming exists in the entire body. The conclusion seems to be inconsistent with the previous viewpoint that most power is generated in the anterior region, while the posterior region performs like a transmitter. However, based on the equations set up in our model, the anterior region equations have smaller curvature, implying that the simulated muscle in this region has smaller strain when it is contracted, thus less positive work is done. Moreover, during steady swimming state, red muscle dominates the swimming motion; if the main muscle power is generated in the anterior part, loss of energy in the form of heat occurs in the process of force transmission towards the tail, which might increase the burden of red muscle as it powers the entire steady swimming process. Given that muscle functions vary among different species, our results need to be further tested with the help of biological analysis. To some extent, our developed tool can mimic the mutual interactions of real

fish with the surrounding fluid and thus allows investigation of the relationship between fish body mechanical force and torque and its swimming behaviours. Using this approach, our future work would focus on evaluating potential analgesic drugs for pain relief and neuroactive drug effects on fish behaviours, which might help to understand functions of nervous system.

The second step includes statistical and numerical analysis on protection of Gyp against acetic acid damage on zebrafish larvae. Our quantifications of kinematics and internal muscle mechanics assist the Real-time PCR results on this protection. Specifically, the qRT-PCR data we have gathered demonstrated that Gyp mediated oxidative stress and inflammation in acetic acid-treated zebrafish larvae through increasing the expression of antioxidant genes and inflammatory cytokine genes. With numerical analysis, we have quantified the protection of Gyp against acetic acid with comparisons of velocity, locomotion activity and power consumption along fish body and comply with biological results. Considering part of the results are difficult to acquire from standard experiments, together with the cheaper cost and faster and more flexible preparations of CFD simulation, we are confident to say that our method could potentially be used to evaluate the effects of drugs on zebrafish behaviours prior to any biological experiments to assist the evaluation and development of therapeutic drugs for neuropathic pain.

For future work, we intend to study another possible factor that might influence the accuracy of our results, the fish body stiffness, which has not been taken into account in the present research. Previous studies on stiffness include the flexural stiffness of superficial neuromasts (McHenry and van Netten, 2007) used for detections of surrounding fluid, and fish body visco-elastic property predictions and related muscle mechanical behaviour based on continuous beam model (Zhang et al., 2014). The body stiffness of aquatic animals could be adjusted at specific positions in order to optimize their swimming performance such as the maximum forward speed and minimum energy cost (Tytell et al., 2016), and subtle changes in fish model can have

a significant impact on the swimming performance (Li et al., 2016). However, the distribution of visco-elastic properties, i.e. stiffness and damping coefficients along the fish body, are difficult to measure precisely, thus the mutual contributions from visco-elastic properties to the optimized swimming performance cannot be determined individually. Moreover, it is technically difficult to observe subtle body curvature changes. Different fish species may have different stiffness and damping characteristics for different purposes, such as for acceleration/deceleration or cruising swimming (Eric.D.Tytell et al., 2010). Based on our current research, the study of passive contribution to fish forward swimming might give us inspirations on some uncertainties, especially the mechanical power distribution, i.e. muscle power generation along the body. Considering the importance of body stiffness for a better understanding of muscle functions in controlling fish swimming, we intend to focus in our future research on the visco-elastic properties at some predicted positions with the help of muscle dissection. To be specific, muscle related adverse medical treatment may have effects on muscle tissues such as shortened or dissolved local muscle fibres (Lin, 2012). By applying predicted stiffness and damping coefficients and comparing these with the live fish tissue properties at those locations, it might be possible to account for the influences on altered swimming behaviours.

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Abbreviations

HTS	High Throughput Screening
Dpf	Days Post-fertilization
BMP	Bone Morphogenetic Protein
AD	Alzheimer's disease
FAD	Familial Alzheimer's disease
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CNS	Central Nervous System
MSS	Morphine Sulfate Solution
NSAIDs	Nonsteroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs
PIV	Particle Image Velocimetry
RPE	Retinal Pigment Epithelium
DPH	Diphenylhydantoin
LED	Light Emitting Diode
Hpf	Hours Post-fertilization
SIMPLE	Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure-Linked Equations
PISO	Pressure Implicit with Splitting of Operator
cDNA	Complementary Deoxyribonucleic Acid
FSI	Fluid-structure Interaction
DAE	Differential-Algebraic Equation
EMG	Electromyography
GSH	Glutathione